

Developing metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts on the environment and society

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Abstract (for dissemination)	The MICS platform prototype for period 2 presents the initial, live, version of the MICS system and its user interfaces that are made available to the public. It is intended to be a demonstration of the technology involved, the impact assessment process and the output and guidance supplied through the MICS assessment tools. It involves and operationalises the assessment methodologies and support derived in WP2, and shows the responses to the validation activities of WP4.				
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1 Executive Summary

The MICS web platform prototype (P2P) describes the initial, or 1.0 version of the platform, which was released live to the public in June 2022. Whilst now openly available to users, it will still be incrementally developed and improved, based on both the feedback from users and the changing priorities of the impact and citizen science fields. This document describes the functional design and specifications of the end-user platform interfaces and structure, utilising open-source solutions for both front and back-end development. To ensure semantic interoperability where possible, the platform follows terminology as defined by D2.5: The MICS ontology, as described in section 6.3 of this document.

2 Introduction

2.1 The context within the MICS Project

The purpose of the MICS project was to investigate how citizen science adds value to research and innovation and, in doing so, better understand the opportunities to improve this process. The project developed several methods and procedures to measure citizen-science impact, modified to be fit for purpose and includes original impact-assessment input features and indicators. To this end, the MICS project will collect a range of different data, both qualitative and quantitative, from several sources.

Deliverable 3.5 presents the initial, live, version of the MICS platform and its associated impact assessment tools and guidance. The platform represents the gateway through which end-users, be they citizen science practitioners, participants, reviewers, policy-makers or other stakeholders, are able to access the MICS impact assessment approach, and better understand the strengths and weaknesses of citizen science projects in terms of impact. It provides a space to discover different citizen science activities and their attributes, understand and utilise the MICS approach when assessing impact, and review standardised impact scores and outputs to help realise potential impact in the future.

Despite being the final deliverable associated with the technical aspects of the platform of the project, it is labelled as the initial, or the 1.0 version of the platform. The reason for this is that although it represents the end of a thorough design process, and has been fully tested to ensure it is suitable for release, it has been designed to be adapted and updated in the future. Significant content, including the assessment input features and indicators and questions presented to the user, and the recommendations and output produced, have been designed to be fully editable beyond the timeline of the project. This is to allow the MICS platform to evolve with the changing themes and associated priorities of both the citizen science and impact assessment fields, ensuring its sustainability and relevance for future citizen science activities and methodologies.

2.2 Context within WP3

WP3 identifies, adapts and develops (as appropriate) impact assessment tools for MICS, based on input from WP2 with respect to relevant concepts and methodologies identified. This input has aided the implementation of the tools and their initial running. The WP has also been informed by the validation activities conducted in WP4.

To incorporate all this information, WP3 has been conducted through several, focused iterations. As such, D3.5 represents the initial, fully-tested version of the MICS platform produced as a culmination of this iterative process. It is informed by D3.1 (Report on the technical requirements), builds on the design considerations of D3.4 (Web platform period 1 - P1P), follows the terminology and ontologies derived through T3.1 (Collaborative synthesis), and integrates the impact assessment approach derived as part of T3.2 (Tools for measuring the impact of citizen science). Representing the initial, live version of the platform, this deliverable will also present the final design of the visualisation tools and user-interaction layer for impact assessment, developed as part of tasks 3.5 (Development of mapping and visualisation tools) and 3.6 (Development of user-interaction layer) respectively in conjunction with partners GeoEcoMar, GEO and RRC.

3 Development team

The development of the MICS platform, and its associated impact assessment tools and methodologies, has taken place over an elongated, iterative process throughout the project. As such,

it has involved both the project partners in terms of conceptual, methodological and functional design, and external expertise to ensure the platform is technically sound, and has a consistent and accessible look and feel. In this section the major roles of each team are presented, with a description of their contribution to the platform development process.

3.1 Conceptual design, methods and functionality

Earthwatch led the development of the platform concept, including the overall look and feel, functionality, and the underlying processes used to evaluate and assess impact. This process was informed by a review of existing web technologies in the fields of citizen science, impact and social media. This work was conducted in close conjunction with WP2, in order to operationalise the impact assessment methods developed into a practical platform application. Factors including the functionality, practicality and aesthetics of the conceptual design were tested and feedback was derived through dialogue with the MICS partners, specifically the case-study activities of WP4.

3.2 Front-end and back-end development

In order to give access to the novel impact assessment tools developed through MICS, both the platform front- and back-end require innovative web solutions not currently or openly available in an 'off-the-shelf' form. Therefore, the MICS project has subcontracted a specialised web-development organisation to produce bespoke solutions for the MICS approach. **MicroAngelo Ltd.**¹ has taken on this role for MICS, specialists in building bespoke web applications that conform with web standards, resulting in highly accessible and future-proof solutions. They have been supported in this development by **GeoEcoMar**, who have been responsible for the thorough testing and documentation of code and frameworks.

3.3 Platform appearance, artwork and asset development

The MICS platform is tasked with communicating a complex and far-reaching array of impact assessment concepts and guidance to the user. As such, the appearance and look of the platform play a key role in communicating this information in an engaging and interesting way, without compromising the functionality and usability of the site. To ensure the appearance is consistent, clear and appealing, **Earthstorm Media**² have been given the role of producing the background graphics, imagery and associated assets for the platform. Furthermore, all designs and assets have gone through an iterative review process, with the MICS partners, case studies and advisory board all involved in providing feedback.

3.4 General testing and review

As explained in the introduction, the development of the MICS platform has been conducted over the majority of the project timeline, through an iterative process involving multiple stages. This iterative process has involved a thorough review process, with feedback used to inform future developments both regarding the design of the platform, and the methodologies it communicates. For the initial stages of development, the **MICS partners, case studies and advisory board** were involved in the platform review. In moving towards the final stages of development, in order to create a platform that is fully tested and suitable for release, a number of **citizen-science coordinators** involved with existing projects were surveyed. This group represent a wide range of citizen-science activities covering a number of different disciplines and approaches, helping to ensure the platform is widely applicable (see appendices 15.1).

¹ MicroAngelo Ltd. <https://microangelo.co.uk/>, accessed 16th June 2022.

² Earthstorm Media: Grounded Creativity. <https://www.earthstormmedia.com/>, accessed 16th June 2022.

4 Platform goals

The objective of the MICS platform, in the context of the project as a whole is:

“... To create a tool which could be used to assess the impact of any citizen-science project, whether it is at the planning stage or years after the project’s completion. Providing a clear framework for measuring impact will help to make citizen science more efficient and effective, reduce costs, and spread the use of citizen science more widely. All of this will strengthen the role played by citizen science in research and informing policy.”

On a practical level, this objective has been translated into the following goals for the platform:

- **Allow users to assess the impact of a citizen-science project across different domains:** Providing several well-designed and intuitive interfaces that capture information on the project through over 200 questions across five domains (environment, economy, governance, science & technology and society) specially adapted from the impact indicators developed as part of WP2.
- **Evaluate the impact of a project from conception to realisation and beyond, seeing how impact changes over time:** The platform should be asynchronous in design, allowing users to update their responses to questions and their project information, and access the impact assessment guidance and evaluations at any point. Users should be able to leave and come back to the process as they wish, with no information lost or repetition required.
- **Allow users to view different projects in the same discipline and compare their impact:** The platform should categorise projects by discipline, and all information regarding impact will be open-access, allowing users to review and compare with other projects, with the aim of sharing best practice and creating a community of learning regarding impact.
- **Produce an impact summary to share with communities, stakeholders, funders and policy makers:** The outputs of the platform in terms of impact assessment should be standardised and accessible, making them easily shareable with all stakeholders. Quantifiable measures of impact should be produced to allow comparison, and combined with qualitative recommendations and guidance tailored to their project needs to improve impact in areas that have been neglected.

5 Development phases

In order to achieve the outlined platform goals described above, an iterative design process was conducted over a period of ~ 30 months from February 2020 to July 2022. This process consists of three main phases, designed to run in parallel with the development and operationalisation of impact assessment indicators in WP2, and the practical application of the MICS approach and associated feedback connected to the case studies of WP4. Figure 1 shows the timings of the major stages of the platform development, along with key deliverable submission dates.

Figure 1: MICS Platform development timeline

Phase 1: Initial design, concept creation and prototyping (Feb – Dec 2020): The first phase of the MICS platform development process involved the initial conceptual and functional design of the main platform pages and aesthetics. This included the storyboarding of user journeys, and the creation of mock-up page designs and assets. The process was guided by feedback from project partners, and the review of existing web solutions involving similar themes. In parallel, the foundational infrastructure for the platform was developed, including front and back-end libraries and databases.

Phase 2: Development and iterative testing and refinement (Jan – Dec 2021): The middle phase of the development involved the prototyping and testing of the major pages and functionality of the platform. This included the development of the project space, assessment interfaces and output, and the design and implementation of user transitions between pages and information. In parallel, the prototypes and developments created were iteratively tested by the project partners, advisory board and case-study activities, with feedback used to refine and improve the platform elements.

Phase 3: Final development, testing preparation for launch (Jan – July 2022): The final phase of development involved final improvements and refinements to platform pages, functionality and aesthetics, in preparation for launch midway through 2022. This included iterative testing and feedback from not only the project partners and case studies, but also a selection of external citizen-science coordinators from a range of different disciplines and backgrounds (see 15.1).

6 Technical framework

Core to the principles of the MICS project is accessibility and the sharing of resources. The structure of the MICS platform is no exception, with open-source repositories, servers and development frameworks being utilised for both the front and back-end of the system. The following technologies have been used for the development of the MICS platform:

- **Apache:** free and open-source cross-platform web server software, released under the terms of Apache License 2.0. Apache is developed and maintained by an open community of developers³.
- **MariaDB:** a community-developed, commercially supported fork of the MySQL relational database management system, intended to remain free and open-source software under the GNU General Public License⁴.
- **Laravel:** a free, open-source PHP web framework, intended for the development of web applications following the model–view–controller architectural pattern⁵.
- **Vue:** an open-source model–view–view model (MVVM) JavaScript framework for building user interfaces and single-page applications⁶.
- **D3:** a JavaScript library for producing dynamic, interactive data visualizations in web browsers. It makes use of Scalable Vector Graphics, HTML5, and Cascading Style Sheets standards⁷.
- **Greensock:** an industry-standard JavaScript animation library that lets you craft high-performance animations that work in every major browser⁸.

³ Apache HTTP Server Project, <https://httpd.apache.org/>, accessed 8th June 2022.

⁴ MariaDB Server, <https://mariadb.org/>, accessed 8th June 2022.

⁵ Laravel: The PHP Framework for Web Artisans, <https://laravel.com/>, accessed 8th June 2022.

⁶ Vue.js: The Progressive JavaScript Framework, <https://vuejs.org/>, accessed 8th June 2022.

⁷ D3 Data-Driven Documents, <https://d3js.org/>, accessed 8th June 2022.

⁸ GreenSock Engaging the Internet, <https://greensock.com/>, accessed 8th June 2022.

- **GNU Octave:** a high-level programming language primarily intended for scientific computing and numerical computation. It has been used by the MICS platform to create the Alquimics algorithm for calculating a project's impact score⁹.

Utilising open-source solutions will ensure the MICS platform is sustainable beyond the duration of the project. This will allow the MICS platform to evolve with the changing themes and associated priorities of both the citizen science and impact assessment fields, ensuring its relevance for future citizen science activities and methodologies.

7 Platform content

In this section, the broad framework of the MICS platform is described, including an overall site map describing the page links and connections, a description of the data and content types, and a taxonomy of the back-end database and its elements and connections. A model-view-controller (MVC) software architecture has been used to develop the platform, a methodology commonly used for developing user interfaces that divide the related program logic into three interconnected elements. This is done to separate internal representations of information from how information is presented to and accepted by the user (Reenskaug & Coplien, 2009). An example of the code-base used for each of the MVC elements can be found in the appendices of this document (see 15.2).

7.1 Site map

Figure 2 shows a user-addressed site map of the MICS platform, giving a systematic view of the pages and links that the site consists of. It has been separated into five main areas: main pages, credentials capture, external links to other information, project data capture, and the assessment process (all colour-coded).

⁹ GNU Octave: Scientific Programming Language, <https://octave.org/>, accessed 29th July 2022.

Figure 2: MICS platform site map

7.2 Content types and data

The MICS platform uses a range of data types and presents information to the user through various interfaces as part of the MICS assessment process. Table 1 describes the data types used, where they are used and their description.

Table 1: MICS platform data types

Name	Type	Platform location	Description
Questions			
Id (links to Question_id)	integer	Backend	For administrators identification
Domain_id	integer	Backend	Identifies the domain of the question
Order	integer	Backend	Indicates the order that the question should be presented to the user
Type	Enum typescript	Backend	Indicates the type of question (multiple choice, single choice etc.)
Title	text	Impact assessment domain pages	The text of the question
text	longtext	Backend	Description of the question
Help	longtext	Impact assessment domain pages	Help text presented to the user
Information	longtext	Impact assessment domain pages	Information text presented to the user
Project answers			
Answer_id	integer	Backend	Identifies the answer
Project_id	integer	Backend	Identifies project that answered the question
Answers			
Id (links to Answer_id)	integer	Backend	Identifies the answer
Question_id	integer	Backend	Links answer to the relevant question
Text	longtext	Impact assessment domain pages	The answer text
Order	integer	Backend	Indicates the order that the answers should be presented to the user
Weight	Integer	Backend	Used in the calculation of indicator scores (see section 8.10)
Disabled questions			
Question_id	integer	Backend	Identifies the question to be blocked
Answer_id	integer	Backend	Identifies the associated answers for the blocked question

Locations			
Id	Integer	Backend	Identifies project locations (organisers, participants and observations)
Name	Integer	Backend	Name of locations
Parent_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies location parent (Europe to UK etc.)
Question Recommendations			
Question_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies questions associated with recommendation
Recommendation_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies the recommendation to be displayed
Domains			
Id (links to Domain_id)	Integer	Backend	Identifies domain
Name	Varchar	Backend	Name of domain
Slug	Varchar	Impact assessment domain pages	Text of URL extension for domain
Background	Binary large object	Impact assessment domain pages	Imagery and assets displayed with domain theme
Order	Integer	Backend	Indicates order that domain information is displayed to the user
Projects			
Id (links to Project_id)	Integer	Backend	Identifies the project
Name	Varchar	Project page	Name of project
Shortname	Varchar	All platform	Short name of project (for menus etc.)
Slug	Varchar	Project page	Text of URL extension for project
User_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies projects' user
Description	Longtext	Project page	Description of project
Shortdescription	Varchar	Project page	Shorter bio of project
Featured	Boolean	Home page	Indicates if the project should appear in featured list
Logo	Binary large object	All platform	Logo of the project
Banner	Binary large object	Project page, home page and impact report	Banner image for the project
Startdate	Date	Project page	Start date of the project
Enddate	Date	Project page	End date of the project
Contact	Varchar	Project page	Name of contact for project

Contactdetails	Varchar	Project page	Contact details for contact
Cost	Decimal	Project page	Cost of the project
Funding	Decimal	Project page	Funding received by the project
Uri	Varchar	Project page	Website of the project
Organisers_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies project locations - organisers
Participants_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies project locations – participants
Observers_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies project locations - observers
Roles			
Id	Integer	Backend	Identifies role of user
Name	Integer	Backend	Name of role
Recommendations			
Id (links to Recommendation_id)	Integer	Backend	Identifies the recommendation
Title	Text	Impact report page	Title of the recommendation
Text	Longtext	Impact report page	Text of the recommendation
Domain_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies the domain recommendation refers to
Image	Binary large object	Impact report page	Image associated with recommendation
Minscore	Integer	Backend	Minimum score needed to trigger recommendation
Maxscore	Integer	Backend	Maximum score allowed to trigger recommendation
Results			
Id	Integer	Backend	Identifies result score
Domain_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies domain score refers to
Project_id	Integer	Backend	Identifies project score relates to
Score	Integer	Impact report page, project page	Score project has achieved
Project topic			
Project_id	Integer	Backend	Identifier of the project
Topic_id	Integer	Backend	Identifier of the topic of the project
Topics			
Id (links to Topic_id)	Integer	Backend	Identifier of the topic
Name	Varchar	Home page	The name of the topic
Slug	Varchar	Home page	URL extension for the topic
Order	Integer	Backend	Indicates the order

			that the topic should be presented to the user
Users			
Id (links to User_id)	Integer	Backend	Identifies the user
Name	Varchar	All platform	Name of the user
Email	Varchar	Project page	The email address of the user
Email_verified_at	Datetime	Backend	Date email was verified by user
Password	Varchar	Backend	User password
Remember_token	Varchar	Backend	Caches user for future use
Image	Binary large object	All platform	Image of user
Created_at	Datetime	Backend	Date and time user registered
Updated_at	Datetime	Backend	Date and time user amended credentials
Roles	Integer	Backend	Roles of user

7.3 Database taxonomy

Figure 3 shows a schema of the MICS database, including the content and data types mentioned in the previous section, and a number of interlinked tables based on each platform entity, with their relationships. Where possible the nomenclature of the database and its elements is in keeping with D2.5: A Multilingual Ontology.

Figure 3: MICS database schema

8 Platform design

Building on the overview of the platform described in section 7, this section describes in more detail the design of each of the platform pages outlined in the MICS platform site map. It includes the artwork, assets and illustrations developed, the functionality provided and the data capture techniques used to collect the information described in 7.2.

8.1 MICS home page

The MICS platform home page (<https://mics.tools>) is the first page new visitors will see. It is designed with the standard appearance and functionality of other well-known ‘catalogue’ type websites, with expected links, information and listing of projects that are already part of the MICS

platform. Figure 4 shows the appearance of the MICS home page, and its design, links and functionality.

Figure 4: MICS platform home page

The MICS home page consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Navigation	Links to log in, registration, and project information and creation procedures.	about.mics.tools mics.tools/login mics.tools/register mics.tools/projects/create
B	Current user	Displays the name of the current registered user signed in, or links to log in/register if no current user is signed in.	mics.tools/login mics.tools/register
C	Title and information	Title of the platform, and brief description of its use.	about.mics.tools/howto
D	Project topics	Display projects by the topic they involve (Arts, Biology, Climate, etc.). As an exception, when “All topics” is selected, all projects are displayed, also those with no topic assigned.	NA
E	Featured	A curated list of projects highlighted for	Mics.tools/projects/name

	projects	users to view	
F	Project list	List of all projects that are on the MICS platform, displayable by topic (see D)	Mics.tools/projects/name

8.2 Log in page

As the name suggests, the log-in page (<https://mics.tools/login>) is where users can log in to the MICS platform, giving them access to the project-creation and impact-assessment functionalities described in the platform site map. A single-sign-in approach has been used, allowing users to create an account with existing credentials from well-known, ubiquitous social media sites and other well-known online platforms. Figure 5 shows the log-in page and its different options.

Figure 5: MICS log-in page

The MICS log-in page consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Navigation	Links to home page, login and register procedures.	mics.tools mics.tools/register
B	Single sign-in	Allows users to sign in to the MICS platform through their credentials on other well-known platforms (Google, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and GitHub).	External site verification processes

C	Log in with email	Allows user to log in with an email and password.	mics.tools
D	Register link	Links to register page.	mics.tools/register
E	MICS domains	Animation of the five mics domains through which impact is assessed.	NA
F	Funding information	Description of the project and funding details of the MICS project.	NA

8.3 Register page

The MICS platform register page (<https://mics.tools/register>) has a similar function to the log-in page, allowing users to register with the platform and gain access to the full functionality of the site. It is predominantly designed for users who do not have credentials for the single-sign-in process of the log-in page, or do not wish to share information with external sites. Figure 6 shows the register page and its data fields.

Figure 6: MICS register page

The MICS register page consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Navigation	Links to home page, login and register procedures.	mics.tools mics.tools/login
B	Your name capture	Field used to identify the user that is not seen publicly.	NA
C	Credentials	Fields allowing users to create platform credentials through the standard email and password method.	NA
D	Register button	On clicking, it confirms the registration and activates the verification process (through email to the user's chosen account).	NA
E	Funding	Description of the project and funding	NA

8.4 about.mics.tools

Accessed through the link on the MICS platform home page (see 8.1, location A), [about.mics.tools](#) is an external link that takes the user to a CMS-controlled MICS project website. On this site, more detailed information regarding the MICS project as a whole, the assessment framework, MICS case studies and the impact input features and indicators used can be found. This includes various guides, resources and training regarding impact, and FAQs regarding the MICS platform. Although this document will not describe in detail the external project site and links, Figure 7 below shows an example page from [about.mics.tools](#).

Figure 7: [about.mics.tools](#) example page - Where to find help

8.5 Create a project page

Once registered on the system, either through the single sign-in or registration process, users can then create a space for their project through the home page 'Create project' link. Doing so starts the *create a project* process (<https://mics.tools/projects/create>), designed to capture a range of information about the project to both display on the project page, and to categorise the project in order to enable querying and sorting functions. Figure 8 and Figure 9 show the 'create a project' page (top and bottom section), and the input fields requested of the user.

Topics (the areas of citizen science that this project relates to)

Select all | Deselect all

Start Date (can be in the future. If the project starts with a grant, this is the start date of the funding)

End Date (leave this blank if the project is ongoing)

Contact name (who to contact if someone wants to know more about the project)

Contact email

Total cost
(the total cost of the project includes money that comes both externally, and internally from the organisation(s) managing the project)

\$/£/€ 0

External funding
(external funding is money that comes from outside the organisation(s) managing the project)

\$/£/€ 0

Project URL (link to website or page for more project information)

Organisers' location
(Organisers are the individuals or entities responsible for running the project, for example the project's partners; select their location by country, continent, or worldwide)

Select all | Deselect all

Save

Figure 9: Mics create a project page (bottom section)

The MICS *create a project* page consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Current user	Indicates the name of the user who is currently signed in to the platform. Activates a drop-menu menu allowing the user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edit profile – change log-in credentials Log out of the platform, and sign in as a different user 	mics.tools/frontend/profile mics.tools
B	Project data capture	Input fields that capture data on the project, for display and categorisation	NA

purposes. They include:

- Project name – the name of the citizen-science project
- Short name – a short name that appears in URLs and menus
- Project address – the MICS address for the project
- Project description – a description of what the project involves, the science involved etc.
- Logo image – a logo for the project, for display purposes
- Banner image – a banner image to display on the project page
- Topics – the topics involved in the project, for cataloguing
- Start date – the start date of the project
- End date – the end date of the project, if there is one
- Contact name – a contact person for the project
- Contact email – an email for the contact person
- Total cost – the cost of the project including internal and external funding
- External funding – the amount of external funding awarded to the project
- Project URL – the web address of the project page (if one exists)
- Location – the location of project organisers, participants and the observations collected if suitable

C	Save button	On clicking, saves the project information captured to the MICS back-end database, and creates the project on the platform.	mics.tools/projects/name
---	-------------	---	---

8.6 Project space pages

Once a user of the MICS platform has completed the 'create a project' process, a project page (<https://mics.tools/projects/name>) is produced based on the information submitted. As such, the project page is unique for each project, allowing the user to view and share information on the project, and access the impact assessment tools of the MICS approach. In keeping with the MICS ethos, the project pages are completely open access, allowing users to view different projects, their approaches and compare impact across the five domains. Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the project

page details (top and bottom sections, project details and impact assessment), and the functionality provided.

The screenshot displays the iMars project page with several annotated sections:

- A:** User profile 'James Sprinks' in the top right corner.
- B:** Navigation menu on the left with links for 'Home', 'About', and 'Project catalogue', and a 'Go to assessment' button.
- C:** Project banner area featuring the iMars logo and a background image of a Martian landscape.
- D:** Project details box containing:
 - Project start date:** February 2015
 - Project end date:** February 2018
 - Project Contacts:** James Sprinks - jsprinks@earthwatch.org.uk
 - Project URL:** <http://www.i-mars.eu/index.php>
 - Impact Assessment progress:** 100% complete
 - An 'Edit' button in the bottom right corner.
- E:** Project Description section with the following text:

The Citizen Science component of the iMars project, Mars in Motion, was created through the Zooniverse's Panoptes framework to allow volunteers to look for and identify changes on the surface of Mars over time. 'Mars in Motion' has been developed to complement the results of automated data mining analysis software, both by validation through the creation of training data and by adding context - gathering more in-depth data on the type and metrics of change initially detected.

Below the text is a side-by-side comparison of two grayscale images of a Martian slope streak, separated by a vertical black line. The caption reads: 'Before and after images of a Martian slope streak.'

Figure 10: MICS project page (top section - project details)

Figure 11: MICS project page (bottom section - impact assessment)

The project page consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Current user	Indicates the name of the user who is currently signed in to the platform. Activates a drop-menu menu allowing the user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edit profile – change log-in credentials Log out of the platform, and sign in as a different user 	mics.tools/frontend/profile mics.tools
B	Navigation	Links to home page, about.mics.tools , and the impact assessment process.	mics.tools about.mics.tools mics.tools/assessment/name/general
C	Project information	Displays a range of information regarding the	NA

		project (including name, logo, banner, start and end date, contacts, URL) collected as part of the 'create a project' process (see 8.5, location B).	
D	Edit button	Allows the user (if the owner of the project) to edit the information, through the 'create a project' process.	mics.tools/projects/create
E	Project description	Displays the description of the project, including media, collected as part of the 'create a project' process.	NA
F	Impact assessment navigation	Links to the impact assessment process, including direct links to the assessment domain map, the five domains, and the general project indicator questions. Also links to the impact report page (see 8.10).	mics.tools/assessment/name mics.tools/assessment/name/governance mics.tools/assessment/name/economy mics.tools/assessment/name/society mics.tools/assessment/name/science mics.tools/assessment/name/environment mics.tools/assessment/name/general mics.tools/projects/name/summary
G	Project impact	Displays the impact of the project as a score out of 42, across the five domains and as an overall average (scores calculated by impact assessment process).	NA
H	Domain progress	Displays the progress the user has made through the indicators that are part of the impact assessment process (see the following sections).	mics.tools/assessment/name/governance mics.tools/assessment/name/economy mics.tools/assessment/name/society mics.tools/assessment/name/science mics.tools/assessment/name/environment mics.tools/assessment/name/general
I	Funding information	Description of the project and funding details of the MICS project.	NA

If this is the first time the user is seeing the project page (i.e. after they have first created the project on the platform), then a pop-up will display, informing the user of the assessment process and how to access it (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Project page information pop-up

8.7 Domain map page

After signing in to the MICS platform, and creating a project space as per section 8.5, users at this point have access to the MICS impact assessment approach and tools. MICS measures impact by gathering information on over 200 input features across the five domains, presented to users as multiple-choice questions accessed through domain-themed interfaces. The domain map page of the platform (<https://mics.tools/assessment/name>) provides links to each domain, and the subsequent questions that are required to be completed. Figure 13 shows the design of the domain map page, and its interactions.

Figure 13: MICS domain map page

The domain map page consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Current user	Indicates the name of the user who is currently signed in to the platform. Activates a drop-menu menu allowing the user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Edit profile – change log-in credentials Log out of the platform, and sign in as a different user 	mics.tools/frontend/profile mics.tools
B	Project name and logo	Displays the project that is currently signed in to the platform, and links to the corresponding project page.	mics.tools/projects/name
C	Progress dials	Displays the progress the user has made through the indicators that are part of the impact assessment process (see the following section).	NA
D	Domain links	Allows the user to access the impact indicators for each domain (general, society,	mics.tools/assessment/name/governance mics.tools/assessment/name/economy mics.tools/assessment/name/society

science and technology,
economy, environment and
governance).

mics.tools/assessment/name/science
mics.tools/assessment/name/environment
mics.tools/assessment/name/general

8.8 Impact assessment domain pages (general, society, science and technology, economy, environment, and governance)

The MICS platform domain pages (<https://mics.tools/assessment/name/domain>) are the place where the majority of user-interaction with the assessment approach takes place. As such, they have been designed to be as intuitive, easy-to-use and accessible as possible, taking into account the issues and knowledge garnered by the MICS project activities when operationalising the assessment input features and indicators (Parkinson et al., 2022; Sprinks et al., 2021). Each of the domain pages is identical in terms of functionality, but individually themed in terms of appearance and aesthetics to indicate to the user which domain they are currently interacting with. Figure 14 shows the domain page design, and its interactions.

Figure 14: MICS domain page (General domain example)

The impact assessment domain pages consist of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Current user	Indicates the name of the	mics.tools/frontend/profile

		user who is currently signed in to the platform. Activates a drop-menu menu allowing the user to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edit profile – change log-in credentials • Log out of the platform, and sign in as a different user 	mics.tools
B	Project name and logo	Displays the project that is currently signed in to the platform, and links to the corresponding project page.	mics.tools/projects/name
C	Question route/number	Route of indicator questions to be answered by the user, in ascending order. On clicking, it launches question pop-up (see 0).	NA
D	Progress dials	Displays the progress the user has made through the indicators that are part of the impact assessment process (see the following section).	mics.tools/assessment/name/governance mics.tools/assessment/name/economy mics.tools/assessment/name/society mics.tools/assessment/name/science mics.tools/assessment/name/environment mics.tools/assessment/name/general
E	Map button	Allows the user to return to the domain map page.	mics.tools/assessment/name
F	Bottom banner navigation	Links to 'how to play', domain map and users' project page.	mics.tools/how-to mics.tools/assessment/name mics.tools/projects/name

8.9 Question pop-up interface

Through the domain pages described in the previous section, users are asked over 200 questions linked to the impact-assessment input features derived during the MICS project activities. These questions are presented through a pop-up interface design, which includes several functions to assist the user in answering the questions as accurately as possible. Answers to the questions displayed are saved to the back-end database in real-time, allowing the user to come and go to questions, and edit their answers at any time. Figure 15 shows the design of the question pop-up interface, and its features.

Figure 15: MICS question pop-up interface example

The MICS question pop-up interface consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Question title	Informs the user of the question they are answering, and from which domain.	NA
B	Question text	The question for the user to answer, derived from the MICS impact assessment indicators.	NA
C	Question answer options	The list of answer options the user can choose from.	NA
D	Information and help	Links to information and help text and associated resources designed to assist the user in answering the question as accurately as possible, for example:	Pop-up with information and help text

“In this question, we use €, £ GBP, or \$ USD interchangeably because the answers are given as orders of magnitude which make the difference in the exchange rate between the three currencies largely irrelevant. Here's a

*currency converter in case it's helpful:
<https://www.1.oanda.com/currency/converter/>*

E	Question navigation	Buttons that navigate through the questions, left to right: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Previous question • Close pop-up (return to domain) • Next question 	Previous, next question pop-up Domain page
F	Domain assets and aesthetics	Imagery and assets themed around the current domain (in this example, economy), indicating to the user the type of questions that will need to be answered.	NA

8.10 Impact report page

After completing the impact assessment process, by answering the questions presented through the domain pages, users can access a report of their projects’ impact through the impact report page (see location F, 8.6). The report can be accessed independently of how many questions have been answered, and is designed to be applicable throughout the different stages of a project, from conception to completion. At the point the user requests to view their impact report, the data they have submitted through the assessment process is passed to the MICS machine-learning algorithm Alquimics (see section 9), which in turn calculates an impact score for each domain, and an overall average. Additionally, rule-based scores are computed for specific indicators based on users’ answers to relevant questions, the results of which trigger recommendations for each domain regarding how the project can improve its impact further.

Figure 16: MICS impact report - project information section

The MICS project information section of the impact report consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
A	Current user	Indicates the name of the user who is currently signed in to the platform.	mics.tools/frontend/profile mics.tools

		<p>Activates a drop-menu menu allowing the user to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edit profile – change log-in credentials <p>Log out of the platform, and sign in as a different user</p>	
B	Introduction and project logo	Introduction to the impact report, and logo to indicate the project being reported on.	about.mics.tools
C	Project map	Map showing the organiser, participant and observation locations for the project (on a global scale).	NA
D	Project information	Displays a range of information regarding the project (including start and end date, contacts, URL) collected as part of the 'create a project' process (see 8.5, location B).	NA

Rules-based scores E

These scores are calculated based on a set of rules written to combine a specific set of impact metrics on the same theme into a single indicator. A higher score means the project is carrying out more activities related to the theme of the indicator and is, therefore, more likely to have a higher positive impact in this area. Rule-based scores are only calculated for specific themes. Overall assessments can be found below in the machine-learning--based scoring. Descriptions and explanations of impact indicators are provided at about.mics.tools/indicators (e.g., the score is low on economic productivity because the project did not include specific aspects related to improving efficiency). Different scores trigger different recommendations presented in the following section. Also, scores are not linked to project objectives; they try to capture a broad range of impacts even if the project does not consider or care about all of them. All scores are out of 42.

	Impact Indicators F	Impact score (max 42) G	Overall average H
Society	Activeness	32	9
	Involvement	16	8
Governance	Policy	1	9
	Sustainable Development Goals	4	8
Economy	Economic productivity	42	6
	Financial sustainability	42	21
Environment	Environmental awareness	0	7
	Environmental footprint	0	36
Science and technology	Scientific productivity	38	41
	Interdisciplinary science	36	7

Figure 17: MICS impact report - rule-based scores

The MICS rule-based scores section of the impact report consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
E	Rule-based scores description	A description of what the rule-based scores are, how they are calculated and a link to further information regarding their derivation.	about.mics.tools
F	Impact indicators	Titles of the indicators considered, separated by domain.	NA
G	Indicator scores	Scores the project has achieved for each indicator, as derived by the answers given to the associated questions.	NA
H	Overall average	The average score achieved by all projects on the MICS platform for each impact indicator.	NA

Recommendations I

The following recommendations are determined by the scores the project received in the previous section. The recommendations are based on citizen-science best practice as defined in the current scientific literature and how other projects have taken action to improve their impact in specific areas. Of course, following these recommendations does not guarantee the project will suddenly have a higher impact; it all depends on the specific context of each project, but the might provide helpful inspiration.

Society	J Activeness	The activeness of participants within a project is an important aspect of citizen science. Activeness depends on participants being aware that they are contributing to a project, having a lot of responsibility in the project, and being satisfied with the process of participation. This project should ensure that all aspects of activeness have been considered.
	Involvement	The degree of involvement of participants in a project is an important aspect of citizen science, and includes involving participants in multiple stages of the project, offering them multiple activities to take part in, and offering different levels of involvements depending on individual interests and availability. This project should consider whether there are more stages of the project that participants could be involved in [see co-design]
Governance	Policy	It looks like policy influence might not be a priority for the project. Of course, not every project can affect policy and some projects have a large impact on governance without ever interacting with official policy. If you're interested in the idea of citizen science as a form of socio-technical governance you can read more in this paper . If the project is interested in influencing policy it could find inspiration from example projects in this report . It might not be a viable option if the project has already started, but citizen-science projects most often have success influencing policy when specific policies are considered in the design of the project and policy makers are engaged from the start of the project. There is more information available on these recommendations here [Mollie's recommendations].
Economy	Economic productivity	It is great that the project has produced outputs that contribute to the economy through industry, commerce, innovation or technological development. If you haven't already, it might be worth considering any legal implications through a dedicated IPR plan.
	Financial sustainability	Well done! The project has a high score due to forward thinking in creating an exploitation plan, planning sustainability activities to prolong the projects' influence and fully appraising any recurring costs and maintenance.
Environment	Environmental awareness	Being environmentally aware means understanding how our behaviour impacts the environment and committing to making changes to our activities. The project could do more to educate participants on environmental challenges and contribute to participants' awareness of the natural environment, by explicitly disseminating information on sustainable lifestyles.
	Environmental footprint	The project could do more to decrease its material footprint , take measures to reduce its polluting emissions , or use a sustainable procurement policy .
Science and technology	Scientific productivity	Congratulations - in a world of "publish or perish", this project has high scientific productivity. With a large number of publications in high impact-factor journals, the project's research has been well cited, indicating outcomes have been widely shared.
	Interdisciplinary science	By working across multiple disciplines, this project is making efforts to promote interdisciplinary ways of working. There is evidence that interdisciplinarity is statistically significantly and positively associated with research impact (Okamura, 2019), largely through the engagement of a wider audience. Keep up the good work!

Figure 18: Mics impact report – recommendations

The MICS recommendations section of the impact report consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
I	Recommendations description	A description of how the recommendations are derived, and their use.	NA
J	Impact indicators	Titles of the indicators considered, separated by domain.	NA
K	Recommendation text	Recommendations for each impact indicator, derived from the rule-based scores calculated for each.	Guidance and resources from both external sources and those created as part of the MICS project on about.mics.tools

Machine Learning Scores L

The following scores were calculated using a statistically-driven machine-learning approach, a type of AI that learns to perform a task by analysing patterns in data. This is an experimental approach to citizen-science impact assessment, and the exact reasoning behind the scores is not explainable. The scores represent a best guess of the impact the project is having in each domain. How can you use the score? Well, this platform gives a common framework for impact assessment so you can use the scores: to see how the project's impact evolves over time; to compare the project with others; to report to funders and participants; or for your organisation's internal reporting. All scores are out of 42.

Figure 19: Mics impact report - machine learning scores

The MICS machine learning scores section of the impact report consists of the following parts:

Location	Title	Functionality	Links to
L	Machine learning scores description	A description of how the machine learning scores are derived, and their use.	NA
M	Domain scores	Scores the project has achieved for each indicator, as derived by the Alquimics machine-learning algorithm (see section 9).	NA
N	Total score	The average score achieved by the project across the domains.	NA
O	Funding information	Description of the project and funding details of the MICS project.	NA

9 Alquimics – The MICS machine-learning algorithm

As has been demonstrated through the description of the platform, attempting to measure the impact of citizen science is a complex issue involving a wide-ranging number of themes, input features, and associated indicators. As such, manually identifying all of the connections and links between such a large number of input features, and a project's relationship with them, is virtually impossible. To address this issue, the MICS platform uses a *machine-learning algorithm* to identify connections and links between the input features, the projects' relationship to them and the project's impact. Called Alquimics, it is stored on the platform back-end and is activated when the user accesses the *impact report* page of the platform (see section 8.10). It takes as its input the users' answers to the over 200 questions (input features) presented on the platform, and outputs an impact score out of 42 for each domain which is then presented to the user.

However, using this approach the MICS team faced a defining question: Which parts of the platform's brain should be handcrafted and which should employ machine learning? Handcrafting is the more traditional approach, in which scientists painstakingly write extensive sets of rules to guide AI's understanding and assessments. Statistically-driven machine-learning approaches, by contrast, have the computer teach itself to assess impact by learning from data. Machine learning is a superior method for tackling so-called classification problems, in which neural networks find unifying patterns in noisy data. However, it is especially tough for a machine-learning system because there usually isn't a verifiably correct way to assess impact. Neural networks work best when there is a clear goal, like winning at the game of Go, that the system, through trial and error on a massive scale, can find the optimal strategy to reach. Impact assessment has no well-defined goal.

In order to address this issue, Alquimics has been trained through the input and self-derived impact ratings of a number of test projects (see section 15.1). Through this process, Alquimics can learn and refine the links between the platform input features and indicators and the projects' impact, with the ultimate goal being to produce a reliable and meaningful impact score. The Alquimics machine-learning algorithm has been created using the GNU Octave language, and an example of its code-base, inputs and outputs can be found in section 15.3. The training of Alquimics will be regularly updated (at least once every six months), as the number of projects on the platform grows and the data they supply increases over time.

10 Accessibility

In keeping with the ethos of the citizen science discipline itself, the MICS platform has been designed to be as accessible as possible. The impact assessment questions presented to users have been tested on case-study projects across Europe to ensure they are clear, concise and intuitive to answer. This process will continue after the project has finished, with feedback collected through the platform for iterative improvement.

The platform uses the Campton and Arial fonts for the majority of its text, both of which display humanist tendencies making them more eligible than grotesque fonts at smaller sizes¹⁰. The platform presents text at as large a size as possible, in clearly definable colours. The colours of the platform are consistent, with the same themes and colours used for each domain throughout the site. The colours that represent each theme have been reviewed to ensure that text is eligible and

¹⁰ A Guide to Understanding What Makes a Typeface Accessible, <https://medium.com/the-readability-group/a-guide-to-understanding-what-makes-a-typeface-accessible-and-how-to-make-informed-decisions-9e5c0b9040a0>, accessed 19th July 2022.

clear using the Colorsafe tool¹¹, and again tested on case-study projects to identify any potential issues.

In terms of the language, the platform has been developed with English at its core, but it is readable by most mainstream browsers (e.g., Google Chrome) for translation. This is true not only of the main, hard-coded text of the general pages, but also of the dynamic text of the impact questions and answers for each domain.

Figure 20 shows the MICS platform home page translated into Italian.

Figure 20: MICS home page translated into Italian

This includes the main introductory text, the topic links to projects down the left-hand side, and even the project titles. Figure 21 shows one of the domain page questions (governance) translated into Chinese. Again this includes not only the navigation aids but also the question and answer options.

The automated translation offered by the browser is far from perfect (for instance, the use of “Casa” for navigation to the home page does not translate well in Italian; “Arts” is translated into “Gli artt”,

¹¹ Color Safe: Empowering designers with beautiful and accessible color palettes based on WCAG guidelines, <http://colorsafe.co/>, accessed 19th July 2022.

which does not mean anything in Italian; and some translations of the titles of the projects are quite embarrassing), but it is of a high-enough standard to render the platform usable across the major global languages.

Figure 21: Governance domain question 5, translated into Chinese

11 Browser support and hosting

The MICS platform and its associated data and code are hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS)¹², allowing both the data and processing capacity to be scalable on demand, and therefore the cost. The AWS instance will be maintained by Earthwatch as the coordinator of the MICS project. Earthwatch is committed to hosting the MICS platform for as long as it serves a purpose, and is being used by the citizen science community (at least until 2030).

The MICS platform and its associated functionality and appearance have been tested and developed predominantly on the Google Chrome browser. Representing almost 80% of web-users¹³, this will ensure the platform is usable to many perspective citizen-science coordinators. Secondary testing took place on the Safari browser, representing Apple computer users (those not using Chrome).

¹² Amazon Web Services, <https://aws.amazon.com/>, accessed 20th July 2022.

¹³ Kinsta: Global Desktop Browser Market Share for 2022, <https://kinsta.com/browser-market-share/>, accessed 20th July 2022.

Regarding other browser technologies, as with all parts of the MICS platform development will be sustained in an iterative manner through user feedback, so any issues that arise will be corrected through this process.

Regarding hardware specifications, the MICS platform has been tested on a range of different laptop and desktop configurations. In terms of screen resolution, this has mostly been tested at 1920 x 1080 and 1366 x 768 pixels, by far the two most common setups globally¹⁴.

12 Ongoing support and maintenance

As with most technologies, issues regarding design often become apparent after the launch of a web platform. Functional, usability and appearance problems are often only discovered when a large user base is exposed to using a large variety of technologies and environments. The MICS platform is anticipated to be no different, and the MICS team will iteratively solve and improve the platform based on unforeseen issues and feedback.

Additionally, as explained in section 6, the platform has been developed using open-source technologies, allowing maintenance tasks to be completed with minimal cost and no proprietary issues. The front and backend code of the platform will also be made fully available to the public through a GitHub repository. This means that users can provide feedback and, where technically able, provide possible solutions and create their bespoke take on the MICS impact assessment approach.

12.1 MICS platform administration layer

The MICS platform has been designed to be as dynamic as possible, allowing the MICS project team to make changes and improvements to impact assessment indicators, questions, guidance and the recommendations provided as the shape of the impact and citizen science disciplines evolve. This is done through the platform administration layer.

12.1.1 User management

The user management part of the administration allows administrators to grant permissions and assign roles to the platform users, as well as delete and edit user credentials as necessary. Figure 22 shows the user-management permissions screen, with the view-edit-delete options for each permission type. This functionality is repeated for roles and users as required.

¹⁴ Statcounter GlobalStats: Desktop Screen Resolution Stats Worldwide – June 2022, <https://gs.statcounter.com/screen-resolution-stats/desktop/worldwide>, accessed July 20th 2022.

Figure 22: MICS administration layer - user management

12.1.2 Domain management

The administration layer also allows administrators to control the domains of the platform, within which the questions for assessing impact are presented to the user.

Figure 23: MICS administration layer - domain management

As can be seen in Figure 23, administrators have as before the standard view-edit-delete options for each domain. Within this functionality, an ID number can be set for identification purposes, the name of the domain, a slug which controls the URL extension for the related domain page, and the background image that appears on that domain page. An order can also be set for the domains of the platform, which relates to the Alquimics output of the calculated domain scores (see section 9).

12.1.3 Question management

The question management screen is perhaps the hub of the MICS platform, as the place where the impact assessment questions can be created, edited and presented to the user. Through this functionality administrators can assign an ID, a domain and a title for the question, as well as the order that they are presented to the user. Additionally help and information text can be created regarding the question and presented to the user through the domain question pop-up interface (see section 8.9). The type of question can also be set here, in terms of single-answer, multiple-answer and so on. Figure 24 shows the question management interface and its functionality.

	ID	Order	Domain	Type	Title	
<input type="checkbox"/>	336	35	Governance	Category (Single Answer)	244	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	335	0	General	Category (Single Answer)	Test_intro question	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	333	21	Science and technology	Category (Multiple Answer)	539	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	332	21	Science and technology	Category (Multiple Answer)	521	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	330	9	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	309	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	329	10	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	310	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	328	11	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	311	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	327	13	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	313	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	326	14	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	314	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	325	17	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	317	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	324	18	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	318	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	323	8	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	308	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	322	19	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	319	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	321	7	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	307	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	320	20	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	320	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	319	19	Science and technology	Category (Multiple Answer)	519	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	318	21	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	321	View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	317	6	Economy	Category (Single Answer)	306	View Edit Delete

Figure 24: MICS administration layer - question management

12.1.4 Answer management

Similar in functionality to the question management interface, the answer management screen allows the administrator to create question answers, assign them to a question, set an ID, and again set the order that they appear to the user. It also displays which projects that are on the platform have selected each answer as their choice. Not only can administrators create text for the answers, but a weighting can also be assigned to be used for the rules-based scores of the impact assessment report (see section 8.10).

Figure 25 shows the answer management interface and its functionality.

Add Answer

Answer List

Show 100 entries [Select all](#) [Deselect all](#) [Copy](#) [CSV](#) [Excel](#) [PDF](#) [Print](#) [Columns](#) [Delete selected](#) Search:

<input type="checkbox"/>	ID	Order	Question	Text Value	Weight	Projects	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1151	3	305	No, the nature of the project does not allow for the generation of new jobs (e.g. it is entirely community run)	0	Creek Kikos	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1150	3	244	I don't know	0		View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1149	2	244	No	0	CookCloud P4Craters Monquito Alert	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1148	1	244	Not yet	0		View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1147	0	244	Yes	0		View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1146	1	234	Not yet	0		View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1145	0	124	Online meetings	0	Marzenego-MICS CookCloud CoAct TF	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1144	18	240	None of the above	0	CiclopsEyeOnWater P4Craters	View	Edit	Delete

Figure 25: MICS administration layer - answer management

12.1.5 Topic management

The topic management interface is where administrators can set the topics of the MICS platform, which can be selected by users to represent their project, and subsequently used for querying and searching by visitors to the platform home page (see section 8.1).

Add Topic

Topic List

Show 100 entries [Select all](#) [Deselect all](#) [Copy](#) [CSV](#) [Excel](#) [PDF](#) [Print](#) [Columns](#) [Delete selected](#)

<input type="checkbox"/>	ID	Order	Name	Topic address	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	12	9	Science of citizen science	citizen-science	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	11	11	Space	space	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	10	8	Physics	physics	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	4	Language	language	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	10	Social Science	social-science	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	7	Nature	nature	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	6	Medicine	medicine	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	5	Literature	literature	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	3	History	history	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	2	Climate	climate	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	1	Biology	biology	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	0	Arts	arts	View	Edit	Delete

Showing 1 to 12 of 12 entries

Figure 26: MICS administration layer - topic management

Figure 26 shows the topic management screen and its functionality. Administrators can create, edit or delete a topic, set an ID, and the URL extension to display its search results (topic address). An order can also be set which controls how the topics appear on the MICS home page.

12.1.6 Project management

The project management interface allows administrators to control the information held on each of the citizen science projects that have been created by users on the platform. From here, all of the descriptive data captured regarding a project (see section 8.5) can be viewed and edited.

Figure 27 shows the project management screen, and its functionality.

ID	Project name	Short name	Project address	User	Email	Featured	Logo image	Banner image	Start Date	End Date	Contact name	Contact email
58	Sasha Woods	SW	sw	Sasha Woods	swoods@earthwatch.org.uk	<input type="checkbox"/>						
57	Mosquito Alert	Mosquito Alert	mosquitoalert	Mosquito Alert	mosquitoalertproject@gmail.com	<input type="checkbox"/>			January 2014		Frédéric Bartumeus	fbartu@ceab.csic
56	Kenya	Kenya	kenya	Luigi Ceccaroni	compartimos@gmail.com	<input type="checkbox"/>						
55	Creek Rákos Citizen Science project	Creek Rákos	creek-rakos	Test Balázs	balazs.kozak@geonardo.com	<input type="checkbox"/>			August 2020	October 2021	Balázs Kozák	zoldxvi@gmail.co
54	Tiny Forest	TF	tinyforest	Victor Beumer	vbeumer@earthwatch.org.uk	<input type="checkbox"/>			March 2020		Daniel Hayhow	dhayhow@earthw
53	Tanzania	Tanzania	tanzania	Luigi Ceccaroni	compartimos@gmail.com	<input type="checkbox"/>						
52	CoAct	CoAct	coact	CoAct	coact@zsi.at	<input type="checkbox"/>			January 2020			
50	Test - Georgia Fields	Test 1	test-1	Georgia Fields	georgiaa.fields@gmail.com	<input type="checkbox"/>			June 2022		Georgia Fields	

Figure 27: MICS administration layer - project management

In addition to the normal view-edit-delete functionality, administrators can also set a project to ‘featured’, meaning the project will appear on the featured list of the platform home page.

12.1.7 MICS platform recommendations

The recommendations interface provides the functionality enabling administrators to create new indicators for the rules-based scores of the impact report, and the recommendations associated with them that are presented to the user.

Figure 28 shows the functionality of the recommendations screen. Beyond the general view-edit-delete options, administrators have to follow a multi-stage process to create a new indicator and its associated recommendations, as follows:

- **Create a new indicator** – giving it a name, setting its domain and a label that appears on the impact report. A check-box indicates to the platform that the current element is an indicator and not a recommendation.
- **Set the associated questions** – attach the questions whose answers will determine the indicator score.
- **Create recommendations** – giving them a name, creating the recommendation text and associated guidance, and attaching them to an indicator by setting the corresponding label.
- **Set recommendation triggers** – for each recommendation, set a minimum and maximum indicator score within which the recommendation is presented to the user. Scores are calculated through the weightings set for each answer to the associated questions (see section 12.1.3).

Recommendation List											
Show 100 entries Select all Deselect all Copy CSV Excel PDF Print Columns Delete selected Search:											
ID	Domain	Title	Label	Questions	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Indicator				
<input type="checkbox"/>	56	Environment	Environmental awareness-mid	Environmental awareness	404 405 406 407	6	38	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	55	Environment	Environmental footprint-mid	Environmental footprint	401 402 403 409	9	34	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	54	Society	Involvement-mid	Involvement	401 402 403	10	30	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	53	Society	Activeness-mid	Activeness	404 405 412	12	33	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	52	Governance	Policy-v loq	Policy	234 235 236 237	-1	8	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	51	Governance	Policy-low	Policy	234 235 236 237	7	20	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	50	Governance	Policy-middle 2	Policy	234 235 236 237	19	32	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	48	Science and technology	Interdisciplinarity-high	Interdisciplinary science	501 502	19	43	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	46	Science and technology	Interdisciplinarity-low	Interdisciplinary science	501 502	-1	20	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	45	Science and technology	Scientific productivity-high	Scientific productivity	510 512 513 515 126	29	43	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	43	Science and technology	Scientific productivity-low	Scientific productivity	510 512 513 515 126	-1	7	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	42	Science and technology	Interdisciplinarity-indicator	Interdisciplinary science	501 502	0	42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	41	Science and technology	Scientific productivity-indicator	Scientific productivity	510 512 513 515 126	0	42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	40	Economy	Financial sustainability-high	Financial sustainability	312 315 324 325	32	43	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	39	Economy	Financial sustainability-middle	Financial sustainability	312 315 324 325	9	33	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	38	Economy	Financial sustainability-low	Financial sustainability	312 315 324 325	-1	10	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	37	Economy	Economic productivity-high	Economic productivity	316	42	421	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	36	Economy	Economic productivity-middle	Economic productivity	316	21	43	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	35	Economy	Economic productivity-low	Economic productivity	316	-1	22	<input type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	34	Economy	Financial sustainability-indicator	Financial sustainability	312 315 324 325	0	42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	33	Economy	Economic productivity-indicator	Economic productivity	316	0	42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	View	Edit	Delete

Figure 28: MICS administration layer - recommendations

12.1.8 Countries management

The Countries management interface allows administrators to set the countries and regions users can select for organiser, participant and observation locations during the ‘create a project’ process. Here, the name of the country or region can be set and an ID, along with a short code, which will normally be taken from the ISO 3166 international standard¹⁵.

Figure 29 shows the design and functionality of the Countries management interface.

¹⁵ Country ISO 3166 codes, <https://www.iban.com/country-codes>, accessed 22nd July 2022.

Add Country											
Country List											
Show	100	entries	Select all	Deselect all	Copy	CSV	Excel	PDF	Print	Columns	Delete selected
ID		Name		Short Code							
<input type="checkbox"/>	248	Worldwide		ww							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	247	South America		csa							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	246	Europe		ceu							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	245	Asia		cas							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	244	Antarctica		can							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	243	Oceania		coc							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	242	North America		cna							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	241	Africa		caf							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	240	Zimbabwe		zw							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	239	Zambia		zm							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	238	Yemen		ye							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	237	Western Sahara		eh							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	236	Wallis and Futuna		wf							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	235	Vietnam		vn							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	234	Venezuela		ve							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	233	Vatican		va							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	232	Vanuatu		vu							View Edit Delete
<input type="checkbox"/>	231	Uzbekistan		uz							View Edit Delete

Figure 29: MICS administration layer - countries management

12.1.9 Blocklist management

Due to the over-arching and crossover of themes regarding the impact assessment questions, some potential answers will render other questions non-applicable. For instance, if a user were to answer “No” to “Does the project contribute towards SDGs?”, it would not make sense to then present the user with several questions on the project's contribution to the SDGs. Blocklist logic is a feature that changes which questions a user sees next based on how they answer the current question. The blocklist management creates a custom set of active questions that varies based on a user’s answers.

This blocklist pattern varies based on rules that the administrators define for the user in the skip-logic management interface. Figure 30 shows this skip-logic management interface and functionality.

Add Blocklist												
Blocklist List												
Show	100	entries	Select all	Deselect all	Copy	CSV	Excel	PDF	Print	Columns	Delete selected	Search:
ID		Answer		Question								
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	Life on land		427 428							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	Marine water		425 426							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	Responsible consumption and production (including food waste and chemical pollution)		423 424							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	Air quality		421 422							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	Sustainable cities and communities		419 420							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	Affordable and clean energy		418							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	Freshwater		416 417							View Edit Delete	
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	Sustainable agriculture		415							View Edit Delete	

Showing 1 to 8 of 8 entries Prc

Figure 30: MICS administration layer - skip-logic management

As can be seen, administrators can select the answer and its ID (the ID field links to the question involved, in case multiple questions have the same answer) that triggers the blocking of questions, and then list the subsequent questions to be blocked. The normal view-edit-delete functionality also exists regarding any blocklists that have already been created on the platform.

12.1.10 Results management

The results management interface stores the Alquimics results for each project (see section 9), for each of the impact domains (science and technology, environment, economy, governance and society). Administrators can edit the impact score of each project for any domain here, as well as delete or add new results as appropriate.

Figure 31 shows the results management interface and its functions.

ID	Domain	Project	Score	
216	Science and technology	TF	20	View Edit Delete
215	Environment	TF	19	View Edit Delete
214	Economy	TF	6	View Edit Delete
213	Governance	TF	23	View Edit Delete
212	Society	TF	28	View Edit Delete
211	Science and technology	HTest1	26	View Edit Delete
210	Environment	HTest1	15	View Edit Delete
209	Economy	HTest1	8	View Edit Delete
208	Governance	HTest1	18	View Edit Delete
207	Society	HTest1	22	View Edit Delete
206	Science and technology	TM22	26	View Edit Delete
205	Environment	TM22	15	View Edit Delete
204	Economy	TM22	8	View Edit Delete
203	Governance	TM22	18	View Edit Delete
202	Society	TM22	22	View Edit Delete
201	Science and technology	Tanzania	26	View Edit Delete
200	Environment	Tanzania	15	View Edit Delete
199	Economy	Tanzania	8	View Edit Delete

Figure 31: MICS administration layer - results management

Also, from this interface, administrators can trigger a re-training of the Alquimics algorithm. By pushing the “Train Neural Net” button, all of the answers for the projects selected are sent to Alquimics, along with the assigned results, to train the algorithm for future project calculations.

13 Future development

The World Wide Web and its services are ever-evolving, and so are the technologies that support it. Platforms like MICS need likewise to be ever-evolving, aware of new systems and technologies to ensure services are sustained and remain relevant.

The open-source nature of the technologies used for the MICS platform ensures that the MICS partners, specifically Earthwatch as coordinator, are able to perform development tasks on the base code to ensure that it remains relevant and usable.

Furthermore, the base code and guidance on its development and use have been made openly available on GitHub (see section 12). This means that beyond the original MICS project team, any stakeholder, or user in general, can download a copy of the platform and create their own, bespoke developments and functionality to fit their specific needs.

13.1 Development wish list

During the development cycle of the MICS platform, it has become apparent that there are many functionalities and design considerations that whilst beneficial to include, were not realistic to implement in the time frame of the project. Therefore, a development wish list was created for development that can be continued after the project's end, perhaps guided by user feedback after the platform launch. This list will be added to continually as the platform garners a larger user base and contributes to the citizen science domain.

Future development goals already identified include:

- Optimisation for mobile platforms – ensuring users can access and contribute to the MICS platform on smartphone technologies.
- Visualisations of impact temporally – showing users how their impact across the domains varies over the lifetime of the project.
- Green hosting – an eventual move away from dependence on AWS, towards a hosting service that has legitimate green credentials.
- Complete translation in more languages – whilst the platform is designed to allow services like Google to translate, by releasing the code on GitHub there is an opportunity for users fluent in any language to perform a more complete translation.

13.2 Platform limitations

The MICS platform has been designed to be applicable to a wide range of citizen science endeavours, but that comes with limitations when dealing with specific or bespoke examples. Many of the impact assessment questions presented to users on the platform might not be relevant, and although the blacklist logic has been designed to limit this issue, some frustration might occur.

MICS does not currently work on mobile platforms; it has not been optimised for them, so issues occur with appearance and functionality. Due to the number of questions presented to the user throughout the impact assessment process (over 200), the decision has been made to focus on desktop technologies. It is hoped that this will be improved after launch as part of the development wish list process (see section 13.1).

Another limitation, linked to both those mentioned above, regards the inability of users to provide free-text answers. Due to the number of questions, and to aid the Alquimics algorithm when identifying connections and patterns when assessing impact, all user-provided answers are categorised through a list of options. This obviously means users cannot provide bespoke, specific answers related to their particular activities, which arguably could provide a more representative impact assessment. To help counteract this issue, users will be encouraged to send feedback to the MICS team when relevant so that answer options can be improved and added to.

The final limitation to mention could conceivably be describing an issue for the domain of citizen science itself, and it is in regards to definitions. Due to the broad nature of citizen science and its activities, it can be challenging to define what impact is and even what a citizen science project is. Citizen science endeavours could be made up of one single project, or several sub-projects that are either conducted concurrently or individually over different timeframes and locations. This poses an

issue for the user regarding how to use the MICS platform. Should questions be answered as one umbrella project, or as sub-projects or phases over time? Ultimately this is a decision to be made by the user, where they should consider the impact they want to measure, and try to be consistent across the different questions they are asked.

However, putting the decision in the hands of the user does give rise to the possibility of ambiguity, potentially causing frustration and confusion when using the MICS platform. The platform then offers guidance on this and other issues on [about.mics.tools], but it is accepted that this limitation will need further consideration over time.

14 References

Ceccaroni, L. and Sprinks, J. (2020). D2.5: A Multilingual Ontology. *Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS (grant agreement No 82471)*

Parkinson S, Woods SM, Sprinks J, Ceccaroni L. (2022). A Practical Approach to Assessing the Impact of Citizen Science towards the Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainability*; 14(8):4676. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14084676>

Reenskaug, T, Coplien, J. O. (2009). The DCI Architecture: A New Vision of Object-Oriented Programming. *Artima Developer*, https://www.artima.com/articles/dci_vision.html, accessed 6th July 2022.

Sprinks, J., Ceccaroni, L., Parkinson, S., Woods, S.M. & Scrieci, A. (2020). D3.4: Participatory adaptive, personalised information-delivery web platform, period – 1 prototype (P1P). *Deliverable report of project H2020 MICS (grant agreement No 824711)*

Sprinks J, Woods SM, Parkinson S, Wehn U, Joyce H, Ceccaroni L, Gharesifard M. (2021). Coordinator Perceptions When Assessing the Impact of Citizen Science towards Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainability*; 13(4):2377. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042377>

15 Appendices

15.1 Existing citizen-science projects involved in platform testing

Project name	Coordinator	URL
Citclops/EyeOnWater	Luigi Ceccaroni	http://www.citclops.eu/
FreshWater Watch	Heather Moorhouse	https://freshwaterwatch.thewaterhub.org/
Tiny Forests	Victor Beumer	https://tinyforest.earthwatch.org.uk/
Outfall Safari	Joe Pecorelli	https://catchmentbasedapproach.org/learn/outfall-safari-guide/
Mars in motion	James Sprinks	http://www.i-mars.eu/index.php
Rákos-patak civil tudomány projekt	Balazs Kozak	https://mics.tools/case-studies/creek-rakos
MICS Italian case-study	Bruna Gumiero	https://mics.tools/case-studies/marzenego-river
MICS Romanian case-study	Albert Scrieci	https://mics.tools/case-studies/carasuhat-wetlands
Naturehood	Ben Williams	https://naturehood.uk/
Planet Four: Craters	James Sprinks	https://craters.planetfour.org/
Cos4Cloud	Jaume Piera	https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/

EU-Citizen.Science	Silke Voigt-Heucke	https://eu-citizen.science/
MONOCLE	Stefan Simis	https://monocle-h2020.eu/
Ground Truth 2.0 (or subsidiary projects)	Uta Wehn	gt20.eu
CitieS-Health	David Kocman	https://citieshealth.eu/
CS Track	Reuma De-Groot	https://cstrack.eu/
ACTION (or subsidiary projects)	Gefion Thuermer	https://actionproject.eu/
WeCount	Giovanni Maccani	https://www.we-count.net/
CoCoast	Jane Delany	https://www.sams.ac.uk/science/projects/cocoast/
D-NOSES	Rosa Arias	https://odourobservatory.org/es/
Mosquito Alert	Frederic Bartumeus	http://www.mosquitoalert.com/en/
Swedish Mass Experiment	Martin Bergman	https://v-a.se/english-portal/projects/activity-projects/researchers-night/mass-experiments/
CSI-COP	Huma Shah	https://csi-cop.eu/
CoAct	Barbara Kieslinger	https://coactproject.eu/
Crowd4SDG	Francois Grey	https://crowd4sdg.eu/
COESO	Smaniotto Alessia	https://coeso.hypotheses.org/
YouCount	Reidun Norvoll	https://www.youcountproject.eu/
CSI on wildlife conservation in Slovenia	Elena Buzan	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/wildlife-conservation/
CSI on the non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) in the UK	Vasiliki Kiparoglou	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/non-alcoholic-fatty-liver-disease/
CSI on energy communities in Germany	Marcela Norena	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/energy-communities/
CSI on infectious disease outbreak preparedness in Italy	Carla Montensano	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/infectious-disease-outbreak-preparedness/
CSI on off-grid renewable energy in rural Uganda	Rhona Nakirya	https://stepchangeproject.eu/citizen-science-initiatives/off-grid-renewable-energy-in-agriculture/
INCENTIVE	Sabine Wildevuur	https://incentive-project.eu/
SEEDS	Claire Murray	https://seedsmakeathons.com/
TIME4CS	Claudia Magdalena Fabian	https://www.time4cs.eu/
cRHS	Marc Naura	https://www.therrc.co.uk/about-crhs

15.2 Example codebase of MICS platform, following the MVC software architecture

15.2.1 Model code and element examples

15.2.1.1 User model

```
<?php
```

```
namespace App\Models;
```

```

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Carbon\Carbon;
use Hash;
use Illuminate\Auth\Notifications\ResetPassword;
use Illuminate\Contracts\Auth\MustVerifyEmail;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;
use Illuminate\Foundation\Auth\User as Authenticatable;
use Illuminate\Notifications\Notifiable;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\HasMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\InteractsWithMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;

class User extends Authenticatable implements HasMedia //,
MustVerifyEmail
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use Notifiable;
    use InteractsWithMedia;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'users';

    protected $appends = [
        'pic',
    ];

    protected $hidden = [
        'remember_token',
        'password',
    ];

    protected $dates = [
        'email_verified_at',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'name',
        'email',
        'email_verified_at',
        'password',
        'remember_token',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    public function getIsAdminAttribute()
    {
        return $this->roles()->where('id', 1)->exists();
    }
}

```

```

    public function registerMediaConversions(Media $media = null):
void
    {
        $this->addMediaConversion('thumb')->fit('crop', 50, 50);
        $this->addMediaConversion('preview')->fit('crop', 120, 120);
    }

    public function userProjects()
    {
        return $this->hasMany(Project::class, 'user_id', 'id');
    }

    public function getEmailVerifiedAtAttribute($value)
    {
        return $value ? Carbon::createFromFormat('Y-m-d H:i:s',
$value)->format(config('panel.date_format') . ' ' .
config('panel.time_format')) : null;
    }

    public function setEmailVerifiedAtAttribute($value)
    {
        $this->attributes['email_verified_at'] = $value ?
Carbon::createFromFormat(config('panel.date_format') . ' ' .
config('panel.time_format'), $value)->format('Y-m-d H:i:s') : null;
    }

    public function setPasswordAttribute($input)
    {
        if ($input) {
            $this->attributes['password'] = app('hash')-
>needsRehash($input) ? Hash::make($input) : $input;
        }
    }

    public function sendPasswordResetNotification($token)
    {
        $this->notify(new ResetPassword($token));
    }

    public function getPicAttribute()
    {
        $file = $this->getMedia('pic')->last();
        if ($file) {
            $file->url          = $file->getUrl();
            $file->thumbnail    = $file->getUrl('thumb');
            $file->preview      = $file->getUrl('preview');
        }

        return $file;
    }

    public function roles()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Role::class);
    }

```

```

protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
{
    return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
}
}

```

15.2.1.2 Topic model

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Topic extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'topics';

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'name',
        'slug',
        'order',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }

    public function projects()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Project::class);
    }
}

```

15.2.1.3 Project model

```

<?php

```

```

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use App\Traits\MultiTenantModelTrait;
use Carbon\Carbon;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\HasMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\InteractsWithMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;
use Illuminate\Support\Str;

class Project extends Model implements HasMedia
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use MultiTenantModelTrait;
    use InteractsWithMedia;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'projects';

    protected $appends = [
        'logo',
        'banner',
    ];

    protected $dates = [
        'startdate',
        'enddate',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'name',
        'shortname',
        'slug',
        'user_id',
        'description',
        'shortdescription',
        'featured',
        'training',
        'startdate',
        'enddate',
        'contact',
        'contactdetails',
        'cost',
        'funding',
        'uri',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
        'created_by_id',
    ];
}

```

```

];

public function registerMediaConversions(Media $media = null):
void
{
    $this->addMediaConversion('thumb')->fit('crop', 50, 50);
    $this->addMediaConversion('preview')->fit('crop', 120, 120);
}

public function projectResults()
{
    return $this->hasMany(Result::class, 'project_id', 'id');
}

public function projectsAnswers()
{
    return $this->belongsToMany(Answer::class);
}

public function user()
{
    return $this->belongsTo(User::class, 'user_id');
}

public function getLogoAttribute()
{
    $file = $this->getMedia('logo')->last();
    if ($file) {
        $file->url          = $file->getUrl();
        $file->thumbnail    = $file->getUrl('thumb');
        $file->preview      = $file->getUrl('preview');
    }

    return $file;
}

public function getBannerAttribute()
{
    $file = $this->getMedia('banner')->last();
    if ($file) {
        $file->url          = $file->getUrl();
        $file->thumbnail    = $file->getUrl('thumb');
        $file->preview      = $file->getUrl('preview');
    }

    return $file;
}

public function getStartdateAttribute($value)
{
    return $value ? Carbon::parse($value)-
>format(config('panel.date_format')) : null;
}

public function setStartdateAttribute($value)
{

```

```

        $this->attributes['startdate'] = $value ?
Carbon::createFromFormat(config('panel.date_format'), $value)-
>format('Y-m-d') : null;
    }

    public function getEnddateAttribute($value)
    {
        return $value ? Carbon::parse($value)-
>format(config('panel.date_format')) : null;
    }

    public function setEnddateAttribute($value)
    {
        $this->attributes['enddate'] = $value ?
Carbon::createFromFormat(config('panel.date_format'), $value)-
>format('Y-m-d') : null;
    }

    public function organisers()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Country::class,
'country_project');
    }

    public function created_by()
    {
        return $this->belongsTo(User::class, 'created_by_id');
    }

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }

    public function topics()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Topic::class, 'project_topic');
    }
}

```

15.2.1.4 Question model

```
<?php
```

```

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\HasMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\InteractsWithMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;

```

```

class Question extends Model implements HasMedia
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use InteractsWithMedia;
    use HasFactory;

    public const TYPE_RADIO = [
        'checkboxes' => 'Category (Multiple Answer)',
        'radiobuttons' => 'Category (Single Answer)',
        'likert' => 'Likert',
    ];

    public $table = 'questions';

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'order',
        'domain_id',
        'type',
        'title',
        'text',
        'help',
        'information',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected static function boot()
    {
        parent::boot();

        /* Question::creating(function ($model) {
            $model->order = Question::max('order') + 1;
        }); */
    }

    public function registerMediaConversions(Media $media = null):
void
    {
        $this->addMediaConversion('thumb')->fit('crop', 50, 50);
        $this->addMediaConversion('preview')->fit('crop', 120, 120);
    }

    public function questionAnswers()
    {
        return $this->hasMany(Answer::class, 'question_id', 'id')-
>orderBy('order', 'asc');
    }
}

```

```

public function questionBlocklists()
{
    return $this->belongsToMany(Blocklist::class);
}

public function domain()
{
    return $this->belongsTo(Domain::class, 'domain_id');
}

public function recommendations()
{
    return $this->belongsToMany(Recommendation::class);
}

protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
{
    return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
}
}

```

15.2.1.5 Domain model

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\HasMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\InteractsWithMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;

class Domain extends Model implements HasMedia
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use InteractsWithMedia;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'domains';

    protected $appends = [
        'background',
    ];

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [

```

```

        'name',
        'slug',
        'order',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    public function registerMediaConversions(Media $media = null):
void
    {
        $this->addMediaConversion('thumb')->fit('crop', 50, 50);
        $this->addMediaConversion('preview')->fit('crop', 120, 120);
    }

    public function domainQuestions()
    {
        return $this->hasMany(Question::class, 'domain_id', 'id')-
>orderBy('order', 'asc');
    }

    public function recommendations()
    {
        return $this->hasMany(Recommendation::class, 'domain_id',
'id');
    }

    public function results()
    {
        return $this->hasMany(Result::class, 'domain_id', 'id');
    }

    public function getBackgroundAttribute()
    {
        $file = $this->getMedia('background')->last();
        if ($file) {
            $file->url          = $file->getUrl();
            $file->thumbnail    = $file->getUrl('thumb');
            $file->preview      = $file->getUrl('preview');
        }

        return $file;
    }

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }
}

```

15.2.1.6 Country model

```
<?php
```

```

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Country extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'countries';

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'name',
        'short_code',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    public function organisersProjects()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Project::class);
    }

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }
}

```

15.2.1.7 Answer model

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Answer extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use HasFactory;
}

```

```

public $table = 'answers';

protected $dates = [
    'created_at',
    'updated_at',
    'deleted_at',
];

protected $fillable = [
    'question_id',
    'text',
    'order',
    'weight',
    'created_at',
    'updated_at',
    'deleted_at',
];

public function answerBlocklists()
{
    return $this->belongsToMany(Blocklist::class);
}

public function question()
{
    return $this->belongsTo(Question::class, 'question_id');
}

public function projects()
{
    return $this->belongsToMany(Project::class);
}

protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
{
    return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
}
}

```

15.2.1.8 Recommendation model

```
<?php
```

```

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\HasMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\InteractsWithMedia;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;

```

```

class Recommendation extends Model implements HasMedia
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use InteractsWithMedia;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'recommendations';

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'domain_id',
        'title',
        'text',
        'minscore',
        'maxscore',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
        'indicator',
        'label',
    ];

    public function registerMediaConversions(Media $media = null):
void
    {
        $this->addMediaConversion('thumb')->fit('crop', 50, 50);
        $this->addMediaConversion('preview')->fit('crop', 120, 120);
    }

    public function domain()
    {
        return $this->belongsTo(Domain::class, 'domain_id')-
>orderBy('order', 'asc');
    }

    public function questions()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Question::class)-
>orderBy('order', 'asc');
    }

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }
}

```

15.2.1.9 Role model

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Role extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'roles';

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'title',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    public function permissions()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Permission::class);
    }

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }
}

```

[15.2.1.10 Result model](#)

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Result extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;

```

```

use HasFactory;

public $table = 'results';

protected $dates = [
    'created_at',
    'updated_at',
    'deleted_at',
];

protected $fillable = [
    'domain_id',
    'project_id',
    'score',
    'created_at',
    'updated_at',
    'deleted_at',
];

public function domain()
{
    return $this->belongsTo(Domain::class, 'domain_id');
}

public function project()
{
    return $this->belongsTo(Project::class, 'project_id');
}

protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
{
    return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
}
}

```

15.2.1.11 Permission model

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Permission extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'permissions';

    protected $dates = [

```

```

        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'title',
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }
}

```

15.2.1.12 Blocklist model

```

<?php

namespace App\Models;

use \DateTimeInterface;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Factories\HasFactory;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\Model;
use Illuminate\Database\Eloquent\SoftDeletes;

class Blocklist extends Model
{
    use SoftDeletes;
    use HasFactory;

    public $table = 'blocklists';

    protected $dates = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    protected $fillable = [
        'created_at',
        'updated_at',
        'deleted_at',
    ];

    public function questions()
    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Question::class);
    }

    public function answers()

```

```

    {
        return $this->belongsToMany(Answer::class);
    }

    protected function serializeDate(DateTimeInterface $date)
    {
        return $date->format('Y-m-d H:i:s');
    }
}

```

15.2.2 View code and element examples

15.2.2.1 Create user view

```

@extends('layouts.frontend')
@section('content')
<div class="container">
    <div class="row justify-content-center">
        <div class="col-md-12">

            <div class="card">
                <div class="card-header">
                    {{ trans('global.create') }} {{
trans('cruds.user.title_singular') }}
                </div>

                <div class="card-body">
                    <form method="POST" action="{{
route("frontend.users.store") }}" enctype="multipart/form-data">
                        @method('POST')
                        @csrf
                        <div class="form-group">
                            <label class="required" for="name">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.name') }}</label>
                            <input class="form-control" type="text"
name="name" id="name" value="{{ old('name', '') }}" required>
                            @if($errors->has('name'))
                                <div class="invalid-feedback">
                                    {{ $errors->first('name') }}
                                </div>
                            @endif
                            <span class="help-block">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.name_helper') }}</span>
                        </div>
                        <div class="form-group">
                            <label class="required" for="email">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.email') }}</label>
                            <input class="form-control" type="email"
name="email" id="email" value="{{ old('email') }}" required>
                            @if($errors->has('email'))
                                <div class="invalid-feedback">
                                    {{ $errors->first('email') }}
                                </div>
                            @endif

```

```

        <span class="help-block">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.email_helper') }}</span>
        </div>
        <div class="form-group">
            <label class="required"
for="password">{{ trans('cruds.user.fields.password') }}</label>
            <input class="form-control"
type="password" name="password" id="password" required>
                @if($errors->has('password'))
                    <div class="invalid-feedback">
                        {{ $errors->first('password') }}
                    </div>
                @endif
            <span class="help-block">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.password_helper') }}</span>
            </div>
            <div class="form-group">
                <label for="pic">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.pic') }}</label>
                <div class="needsclick dropzone"
id="pic-dropzone">
                    </div>
                    @if($errors->has('pic'))
                        <div class="invalid-feedback">
                            {{ $errors->first('pic') }}
                        </div>
                    @endif
                <span class="help-block">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.pic_helper') }}</span>
                </div>
                <div class="form-group">
                    <label class="required" for="roles">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.roles') }}</label>
                    <div style="padding-bottom: 4px">
                        <span class="btn btn-info btn-xs
select-all" style="border-radius: 0">{{ trans('global.select_all')
}}</span>
                        <span class="btn btn-info btn-xs
deselect-all" style="border-radius: 0">{{
trans('global.deselect_all') }}</span>
                    </div>
                    <select class="form-control select2"
name="roles[]" id="roles" multiple required>
                        @foreach($roles as $id => $role)
                            <option value="{{ $id }}" {{
in_array($id, old('roles', [])) ? 'selected' : '' }}>{{ $role
}}</option>
                        @endforeach
                    </select>
                    @if($errors->has('roles'))
                        <div class="invalid-feedback">
                            {{ $errors->first('roles') }}
                        </div>
                    @endif
                <span class="help-block">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.roles_helper') }}</span>

```

```

        </div>
        <div class="form-group">
            <button class="btn btn-danger"
type="submit">
                {{ trans('global.save') }}
            </button>
        </div>
    </form>
</div>
</div>
</div>

</div>
</div>
</div>
@endsection

@section('scripts')
<script>
    Dropzone.options.picDropzone = {
        url: '{{ route('frontend.users.storeMedia') }}',
        maxFileSize: 2, // MB
        acceptedFiles: '.jpeg,.jpg,.png,.gif',
        maxFiles: 1,
        addRemoveLinks: true,
        headers: {
            'X-CSRF-TOKEN': "{{ csrf_token() }}"
        },
        params: {
            size: 2,
            width: 4096,
            height: 4096
        },
        success: function (file, response) {
            $('form').find('input[name="pic"]').remove()
            $('form').append('<input type="hidden" name="pic" value="' +
response.name + '>')
        },
        removedfile: function (file) {
            file.previewElement.remove()
            if (file.status !== 'error') {
                $('form').find('input[name="pic"]').remove()
                this.options.maxFiles = this.options.maxFiles + 1
            }
        },
        init: function () {
@if(isset($user) && $user->pic)
            var file = {!! json_encode($user->pic) !!}
            this.options.addedfile.call(this, file)
            this.options.thumbnail.call(this, file, file.preview)
            file.previewElement.classList.add('dz-complete')
            $('form').append('<input type="hidden" name="pic" value="' +
file.file_name + '>')
            this.options.maxFiles = this.options.maxFiles - 1
@endif
        },
        error: function (file, response) {

```

```

        if ($.type(response) === 'string') {
            var message = response //dropzone sends it's own error
messages in string
        } else {
            var message = response.errors.file
        }
        file.previewElement.classList.add('dz-error')
        _ref = file.previewElement.querySelectorAll('[data-dz-
errormessage]')
        _results = []
        for (_i = 0, _len = _ref.length; _i < _len; _i++) {
            node = _ref[_i]
            _results.push(node.textContent = message)
        }

        return _results
    }
}
</script>
@endsection

```

15.2.2.2 Show user view

```

@extends('layouts.frontend')
@section('content')
<div class="container">
    <div class="row justify-content-center">
        <div class="col-md-12">

            <div class="card">
                <div class="card-header">
                    {{ trans('global.show') }} {{
trans('cruds.user.title') }}
                </div>

                <div class="card-body">
                    <div class="form-group">
                        <div class="form-group">
                            <a class="btn btn-default" href="{{
route('frontend.users.index') }}">
                                {{ trans('global.back_to_list') }}
                            </a>
                        </div>
                        <table class="table table-bordered table-
striped">
                            <tbody>
                                <tr>
                                    <th>
                                        {{
trans('cruds.user.fields.id') }}
                                    </th>
                                    <td>
                                        {{ $user->id }}
                                    </td>
                                </tr>
                            </tbody>
                        </table>
                    </div>
                </div>
            </div>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

```

```

        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th>
                {{
trans('cruds.user.fields.name') }}
            </th>
            <td>
                {{ $user->name }}
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th>
                {{
trans('cruds.user.fields.email') }}
            </th>
            <td>
                {{ $user->email }}
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th>
                {{
trans('cruds.user.fields.email_verified_at') }}
            </th>
            <td>
                {{ $user->email_verified_at
}}
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th>
                {{
trans('cruds.user.fields.pic') }}
            </th>
            <td>
                @if($user->pic)
                    <a href="{{ $user->pic-
>getUrl() }}" target="_blank" style="display: inline-block">
                        
                    </a>
                @endif
            </td>
        </tr>
        <tr>
            <th>
                {{
trans('cruds.user.fields.roles') }}
            </th>
            <td>
                @foreach($user->roles as
$key => $roles)
                    <span class="label
label-info">{{ $roles->title }}</span>
                @endforeach
            </td>

```



```

                <circle cx="250" cy="250" fill="transparent"
r="159.155" stroke="#ccc" stroke-width="60"></circle>
                <circle id="currentprogresscircle"
transform="rotate(-90, 250, 250)" cx="250" cy="250"
fill="transparent" r="159.155" stroke="{{ $domain->colour }}"
stroke-dasharray="{{ $dasharray }}, {{ 1000-$dasharray }}" stroke-
dashoffset="0" stroke-width="60"></circle>
                <text x="50%" y="254" fill="{{ $domain-
>colour }}" dominant-baseline="middle" text-anchor="middle"
class="large"><tspan id='currentprogresstspan'>{{ $domain-
>percentanswered }}</tspan>%</text>
                </g>
            </svg>
        </div>
        @endif
    @endforeach
    <div class="row">
        <ul>
            @foreach ($domains as $domain)
                @if ($domain->id <> $currentdomain->id)
                    <?php
                        $dasharray = 1000 * ($domain-
>percentanswered / 100);
                    ?>
                    <a href="/assessment/{{ $project->slug }}/{{
$domain->slug }}">
                        <svg height="100" viewBox="0 0 850 600">
                            <style>
                                .label {
                                    font: 75px sans-serif;
                                }
                            </style>
                            <g id="currentprogress" class="circle
circle-1">
                                <circle cx="50%" cy="250"
fill="transparent" r="159.155" stroke="#ccc" stroke-
width="60"></circle>
                                <circle transform="rotate(-90, 424,
250)" cx="50%" cy="250" fill="transparent" r="159.155" stroke="{{
$domain->colour }}" stroke-dasharray="{{ $dasharray }}, {{ 1000-
$dasharray }}" stroke-dashoffset="0" stroke-width="60"></circle>
                                <text x="50%" y="254" fill="{{ $domain-
>colour }}" dominant-baseline="middle" text-anchor="middle"
class="large"><tspan>{{ $domain->percentanswered }}</tspan>%</text>
                                <text x="50%" y="495" fill="{{ $domain-
>colour }}" dominant-baseline="middle" text-anchor="middle"
class="label">{{ $domain->name }}</text>
                                </g>
                            </svg>
                        </a>
                    @endif
                @endforeach
            </ul>
        </div>
    </div> <!-- scoreboard -->

```

```

<div id="dotpathdiv">
  <object id="dotpath" type="image/svg+xml" data="{
$currentdomain->background ? $currentdomain->background->getUrl() :
'/defaultbackground.svg' }" ></object>
</div>

<script
src="https://cdnjs.cloudflare.com/ajax/libs/gsap/3.7.1/gsap.min.js">
</script>
<script>
  window.addEventListener('load', function() {
    $.ajaxSetup({
      headers: {
        'X-CSRF-TOKEN': $('meta[name="csrf-
token"]').attr('content')
      }
    });

    dotpath = document.getElementById('dotpath');
    path =
dotpath.contentDocument.getElementById('dotpathpath');

    layer1 =
dotpath.contentDocument.getElementById('Question_Path');

    dots = {{ $currentdomain->domainQuestions->count()
}};

    totallength = path.getTotalLength();
    spacebetweendots = (totallength / (dots+1));

    gsap.set(path, {

      strokeDasharray: totallength,
      strokeDashoffset: totallength
    });

    // unhide the SVG (hidden to stop FOUC)
    dotpath.style.opacity = 1;

    // Animate the line in
    gsap.to(path, {
      duration: 5,
      strokeDashoffset: 0,
      delay: 1
    });

    // Create the dots
    for (var i = 0; i < dots; i++) {
      point = path.getPointAtLength(spacebetweendots *
(i+1));

      var circle =
document.createElementNS("http://www.w3.org/2000/svg", 'circle');
      circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'cx', point.x);
      circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'cy', point.y);
      circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'r', 30);

```

```

        circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'class', 'dot');
        circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'id', 'dot-'+i);

        // And the dot number labels
        var label =
document.createElementNS("http://www.w3.org/2000/svg", 'text');
        label.setAttributeNS(null, 'x', point.x-1);
        label.setAttributeNS(null, 'y', point.y+2.5);
        label.setAttributeNS(null, 'dominant-baseline',
"middle");
        label.setAttributeNS(null, 'text-anchor',
"middle");
        label.setAttributeNS(null, 'style', 'fill: #000;
font-size: 36px; font-family: Halcom-Medium; pointer-events:
none;');
        label.setAttributeNS(null, 'class', 'dotlabel');
        label.textContent = i+1;

        // check for answers
        answerarray = [];

        // Get all children inputs of the question
        questionid = 'question-'+(i+1);

document.getElementById(questionid).querySelectorAll('input').forEac
h(
            element => {if (element.checked)
answerarray.push(element.value)
            };

            // set colour based on if answered or not
            if (answerarray.length < 1) {
                circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'style', 'fill:
#fffdd0; stroke: gray; stroke-width: 5px; cursor: pointer;');
            } else {
                circle.setAttributeNS(null, 'style', 'fill:
gray; stroke: green; stroke-width: 5px; cursor: pointer;');
            }

            layer1.appendChild(circle);
            layer1.appendChild(label);
        }

        // animate the dots in

gsap.from(dotpath.contentDocument.querySelectorAll('.dot'), {
        duration: 1.5,
        delay: 3,
        opacity: 0,
        y: -200,
        stagger: 0.2,
        ease: "expo"
    });

    // animate the dot labels in

```

```

gsap.from(dotpath.contentDocument.querySelectorAll('.dotlabel'), {
    duration: 1.5,
    delay: 3,
    opacity: 0,
    y: -200,
    stagger: 0.2,
    ease: "expo"
});

// add click events to dots

dotpath.contentDocument.querySelectorAll('circle').forEach(item => {
    item.addEventListener('click', (e) => {
        questionid = 'question-
'+(Number(e.target.id.split('-')[1])+1);
        console.log('Qustion Id: '+questionid);
        hideallquestions();

document.getElementById(questionid).style.visibility = 'visible';
    })
    }, false);

function hideallquestions() {

document.querySelectorAll('.question').forEach(question => {
    question.style.visibility = 'hidden';
});
}

function backtomap() {
    window.location.href = window.location + "../";
}

function answerdot(dotid, questionid) {

    answerarray = [];

    // Get all children inputs of the question
    document.getElementById('question-
'+(Number(dotid))).querySelectorAll('input').forEach(
        element => {if (element.checked)
answerarray.push(element.value)
        });

    console.log('answerarray: '+answerarray);

    ajaxurl = "/assessment/{ $project->slug
}}/answer/"+questionid;
    console.log('ajaxurl: '+ajaxurl);

$.ajax({
    type: 'POST',
    url: ajaxurl,

```

```

        data:{projectid:{{ $project->id }},
questionid:questionid, answerarray:answerarray},
        success:function(data){
            // Update right hand side info

document.getElementById('questionsanswered').textContent =
data['questionsanswered'];
            numberquestionsanswered =
Number(data['questionsanswered']);
            numbertotalquestions = Number({{
$currentdomain->domainQuestions->count() }});
            percentcomplete = Math.round(100 *
numberquestionsanswered / numbertotalquestions);

document.getElementById('currentprogressspan').textContent =
percentcomplete;
            strokeDasharray = "" + (1000 *
(percentcomplete/100)) + "," + (1000 * (1-(percentcomplete/100)));
            console.log('strokeDasharray',
strokeDasharray);

document.getElementById('currentprogresscircle').setAttributeNS(null
, 'stroke-dasharray', strokeDasharray);
        }
    });

    // Update the dot colour if there are any answers -
should probably just add/remove class
    dotpath = document.getElementById('dotpath');
    dotnameid = 'dot-'+(dotid-1);
    dot =
dotpath.contentDocument.getElementById(dotnameid);
    console.log('Updating dot with id '+dotnameid);
    if (answerarray.length < 1) { // unanswered
        dot.setAttributeNS(null, 'style', 'fill:
rgb(255, 253, 208); stroke: gray; stroke-width: 5px; cursor:
pointer;' );
        console.log('unanswered');
    } else { // answered
        dot.setAttributeNS(null, 'style', 'fill: gray;
stroke: green; stroke-width: 5px; cursor: pointer;' );
        console.log('answered');
    }
}

</script>

<div><!-- questions -->
<ol class="questions">

    @foreach($currentdomain->domainQuestions as
$key => $question)
        <li class="question" id="question-{{
$loop->iteration }}">
            <div class="questionbox domain-{{
$currentdomain->slug }}">

```

```

                                <h4 class="text-center">{{
$currentdomain->name }}: Question {{ $loop->iteration }}</h4>

                                <div class="questiontext">{!!
$question->text !!</div>

                                <ul class="answers">
                                  @foreach($question-
>questionAnswers as $key => $answer)
                                    <li>
                                      @switch($question-
>type)
                                        @case('checkboxes')
                                            <input
type="checkbox" id="checkboxanswer-{{ $question->id }}-{{ $answer-
>id }}" name="checkboxset-{{ $question->id }}" value="{{ $answer->id }}"
{{ (in_array($answer->id, old('answers', [])) || $project-
>projectsAnswers->contains($answer->id)) ? 'checked' : '' }}>
                                                <label
for="checkboxanswer-{{ $question->id }}-{{ $answer->id }}">{!! $answer-
>text !!</label>
                                                    @break
                                        @case('radiobuttons')
                                            <input
type="radio" id="radioanswer-{{ $question->id }}-{{ $answer->id }}"
name="radioset-{{ $question->id }}" value="{{ $answer->id }}" {{
(in_array($answer->id, old('answers', [])) || $project-
>projectsAnswers->contains($answer->id)) ? 'checked' : '' }}>
                                                <label
for="radioanswer-{{ $question->id }}-{{ $answer->id }}">{!! $answer-
>text !!</label>
                                                    @break
                                        @case('likert')
                                            <input
type="radio" id="likertanswer-{{ $question->id }}-{{ $answer->id }}"
name="likertset-{{ $question->id }}" value="{{ $answer->id }}" {{
(in_array($answer->id, old('answers', [])) || $project-
>projectsAnswers->contains($answer->id)) ? 'checked' : '' }}>
                                                <label
for="likertanswer-{{ $question->id }}-{{ $answer->id }}">{!! $answer-
>text !!</label>
                                                    @break
                                        @default
<span>default</span> - {!! $answer->text !!}
                                            @endswitch
                                        </li>
                                  @endforeach
                                </ul>

                                <div class="submitbuttons">

```

```

        @if (false == $loop->first)
<a href="javascript:void(0);" class=" nextquestion"
onclick="hideallquestions(); answerdot({{ $loop->iteration }},
{{ $question->id }}); document.getElementById('question-{{ $loop-
>iteration - 1 }}').style.visibility = 'visible';"><i class="fa fa-
chevron-left"></i></a>@endif
        <a
href="javascript:void(0);" class="backtoroute"
onclick="hideallquestions(); answerdot({{ $loop->iteration }},
{{ $question->id }});"><i class="fa fa-times"></i></a>
        @if ($loop->last)
        <a
href="javascript:void(0);" class="return-to-map"
onclick="hideallquestions(); answerdot({{ $loop->iteration }},
{{ $question->id }}); backtomap();"><i class="fa fa-map-o" aria-
hidden="true"></i></a>
        @else
        <a
href="javascript:void(0);" class=" nextquestion"
onclick="hideallquestions(); answerdot({{ $loop->iteration }},
{{ $question->id }}); document.getElementById('question-{{ $loop-
>iteration + 1 }}').style.visibility = 'visible';"><i class="fa fa-
chevron-right"></i></a>
        @endif
    </div>

    <ul class="helpinfo"
style="background: url('/{{ $currentdomain->slug }}TL.svg'),
url('/{{ $currentdomain->slug }}TR.svg'), url('/{{ $currentdomain-
>slug }}BL.svg'), url('/{{ $currentdomain->slug }}BR.svg');
background-repeat: no-repeat, no-repeat, no-repeat, no-repeat;
background-position: top left, top right, bottom left, bottom right;
background-size: 15%, 15%, 15%, 15%;">
        @if ($question->help)
        <li
class="helpbutton"><a href="javascript:void(0);"
onclick="document.getElementById('help-{{ $loop-
>iteration }}').classList.toggle('hiddenbox');"><i class="fa fa-
question" title="Help"></i></a></li>
        @endif
        @if ($question->information)
        <li
class="infobutton"><a href="javascript:void(0);"
onclick="document.getElementById('info-{{ $loop-
>iteration }}').classList.toggle('hiddenbox');"><i class="fa fa-info"
title="Info"></i></a></li>
        @endif
    </ul>

</div>
<div class="helpbox hiddenbox"
id="help-{{ $loop->iteration }}">
        {!! $question->help !!}
        <div class="closebutton">

```

```

                <a
href="javascript:void(0);" onclick="document.getElementById('help-
{{$loop->iteration}}').classList.toggle('hiddenbox');" ><i class="fa
fa-times"></i></a>
                </div>
            </div>
            <div class="infobox hiddenbox"
id="info-{{ $loop->iteration }}">
                {!! $question->information !!}
                <div class="closebutton">
                    <a
href="javascript:void(0);" onclick="document.getElementById('info-
{{$loop->iteration}}').classList.toggle('hiddenbox');" ><i class="fa
fa-times"></i></a>
                </div>
            </div>
        </li>
    @endforeach
</ol>
</div><!-- questions -->

    <div id="returnnav">
        <ul class="p-0 m-0 d-flex flex-row justify-content-
between">
            <li><a class="how-to-play"
href="https://about.mics.tools/how-to" target="_blank" rel="help"><i
class="fa fa-question-circle" aria-hidden="true"></i> How to
play</a></li>
            <li><a class="return-to-map"
href="/assessment/{{$ $project->slug }}"><i class="fa fa-map-o" aria-
hidden="true"></i> Go to domain map</a></li>
            <li><a class="return-to-project"
href="/projects/{{$ $project->slug }}"><i class="fa fa-undo" aria-
hidden="true"></i> Return to project page</a></li>
        </ul>
    </div><!-- returnnav -->

</div><!-- container -->
@endsection

```

15.2.2.4 Domain map view

```

@extends('layouts.frontend')

@section('content')

<div class="container">
    <div class="row" style="position: relative;">
        <object id="domainmapsvg" type="image/svg+xml" style="width:
100%; margin: 0;" data="/domain_map.svg"></object>

        <div id="scoreboard">

```

```

        <a href="/projects/{{ $project->slug }}"
id="projectlogo" style="background-image: url('{{ $project->logo ?
$project->logo->getUrl() : '/css/defaultlogo.png' }});"></a>
        <h4>{{ $project->shortname }}</h4>
        <div class="row">

                <ul>
                        @foreach ($domains as $domain)
                                <?php
                                        $dasharray = 1000 * ($domain->
percentanswered / 100);
                                ?>
                                <a href="/assessment/{{ $project->slug }}/{{
$domain->slug }}">
                                        <svg height="100" viewBox="0 0 850 600">
                                                <style>
                                                        .large {
                                                                font: 100px sans-serif;
                                                        }
                                                        .label {
                                                                font: 75px sans-serif;
                                                        }
                                                </style>
                                                <g id="currentprogress"
class="circle circle-1">
                                                        <circle cx="50%" cy="250"
fill="transparent" r="159.155" stroke="#ccc" stroke-
width="60"></circle>
                                                        <circle transform="rotate(-90, 424,
250)" cx="50%" cy="250" fill="transparent" r="159.155" stroke="{{
$domain->colour }}" stroke-dasharray="{{ $dasharray }}, {{ 1000-
$dasharray }}" stroke-dashoffset="0" stroke-width="60"></circle>
                                                        <text x="50%" y="254" fill="{{
$domain->colour }}" dominant-baseline="middle" text-anchor="middle"
class="large"><tspan>{{ $domain->percentanswered }}</tspan>%</text>
                                                        <text x="50%" y="495" fill="{{
$domain->colour }}" dominant-baseline="middle" text-anchor="middle"
class="label">{{ $domain->name }}</text>
                                                        </g>
                                                </svg>
                                </a>
                        @endforeach
                </ul>

        </div>

</div>
</div>
</div>
@endsection

```

15.2.2.5 Home page view

```
@extends('layouts.frontend')
```

```

@section('content')

<div class="container">
  <div class="row">
    <div class="topnav col-2">
      <nav>
        <ul>
          <li class="nav-item"><a class="nav-link"
href="/">Home</a></li>
          <li class="nav-item"><a class="nav-link"
href="https://about.mics.tools">About</a></li>
          <li class="nav-item"><a class="nav-link"
href="/#projects">Project catalogue</a></li>

          @guest
            <li class="nav-item">
              <a class="nav-link" href="{{ route('login')
}}">{{ __('Log in') }}</a>
            </li>
            @if(Route::has('register'))
              <li class="nav-item">
                <a class="nav-link" href="{{
route('register') }}">{{ __('Register') }}</a>
              </li>
            @endif
          @else
            <h5 style="margin-top: 34px">Your projects</h5>
            @if ($myprojects)
              @foreach($myprojects as $key => $project)
                <li class="nav-item">
                  <a class="nav-link"
href="/projects/{{ $project->slug }}"> {{ Str::limit($project->shortname, 10) }}</a>
                </li>
              @endforeach
            @endif
          @endif
          <li class="nav-item"><a class="btn btn-primary p-2"
href="projects/create"><i class="fa fa-plus" aria-hidden="true"></i>
Create project</a></li>

        </ul>
      </nav>
    </div>

    @include('partials.welcome')
  </div>
</div>

<div class="container p-0">
  <div class="card">
    <div id="projects" class="card-header">
      Project catalogue <small class="text-muted">- Take a
look at other projects and their impact</small>
    </div>
  </div>

```

```

<div class="row">
  <div class="bottomnav col-2">

    <nav>
      <h6>Sort projects by:</h6>

      <ul id="topiclist">
        <li>
          <input type="radio" id="topic_showall"
name="topicradios" value="showall" checked>
          <label for="topic_showall">All
topics</label>
        </li>
        @foreach($topics as $topic)
          <li>
            <input type="radio" id="topic_{{
$topic->slug }}" name="topicradios" value="{{ $topic->slug }}">
            <label for="topic_{{ $topic->slug
}}">{{ $topic->name }}</label>
          </li>
        @endforeach
      </ul>
    </nav>
  </div>

  <div class="col projects">

    @if ($projects)
      @if ($featuredcount)
        <h6>Featured projects</h6>
        <ul>
          @foreach($projects as $key => $project)
            @if($project->featured)
              @php
                $topiclist = "";
                foreach ($project->topics as
$topic) {
                  $topiclist .= "topic_ " .
$topic->slug . " ";
                }
              @endphp
              <li class="projectbox {{
$topiclist }}">
                <div
class="bannerwrapper"></div>
                <div
class="logowrapper"></div>
                <a class="btn btn-info"
href="/projects/{{ $project->slug }}">{{ Str::limit($project-
>shortname, 16) }}</a>
            </li>
          @endforeach
        </ul>
      @endif
    @endif
  </div>

```

```

                </li>
            @endif
        @endforeach
    </ul>

    <hr />
@endif
<h6>Project list</h6>
<ul>
    @foreach($projects as $key => $project)
        @if(!$project->featured)
            @php
                $topiclist = "";
                foreach ($project->topics as
$topic) {
                    $topiclist .= "topic_" .
$topic->name . " ";
                }
            @endphp

            <li class="projectbox {{ $topiclist
}}">
                <div class="bannerwrapper"></div>
                <div class="logowrapper"></div>
                <a class="btn btn-info"
href="/projects/{{ $project->slug }}">{{ Str::limit($project-
>shortname, 16) }}</a>
            </li>
        @endif
    @endforeach
</ul>

    @endif
</div>

</div>
</div>
</div>
@endsection

```

15.2.2.6 Profile view

```

@extends('layouts.frontend')
@section('content')

<div class="container">
    <div class="row">
        <div class="col-md-6">
            <div class="card">

```

```

        <div class="card-header">
            {{ trans('global.my_profile') }}
        </div>
        <div class="card-body">
            <form method="POST" action="{{
route("frontend.profile.update") }}">
                @csrf
                <div class="form-group">
                    <label class="required" for="name">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.name') }}</label>
                    <input class="form-control {{ $errors-
>has('name') ? 'is-invalid' : '' }}" type="text" name="name"
id="name" value="{{ old('name', auth()->user()->name) }}" required>
                    @if($errors->has('name'))
                        <div class="invalid-feedback">
                            {{ $errors->first('name') }}
                        </div>
                    @endif
                </div>
                <div class="form-group">
                    <label class="required" for="title">{{
trans('cruds.user.fields.email') }}</label>
                    <input class="form-control {{ $errors-
>has('email') ? 'is-invalid' : '' }}" type="text" name="email"
id="email" value="{{ old('email', auth()->user()->email) }}"
required>
                    @if($errors->has('email'))
                        <div class="invalid-feedback">
                            {{ $errors->first('email') }}
                        </div>
                    @endif
                </div>
                <div class="form-group">
                    <button class="btn btn-danger"
type="submit">
                        {{ trans('global.save') }}
                    </button>
                </div>
            </form>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>
<div class="col-md-6">
    <div class="card">
        <div class="card-header">
            {{ trans('global.change_password') }}
        </div>
        <div class="card-body">
            <form method="POST" action="{{
route("frontend.profile.password") }}">
                @csrf
                <div class="form-group {{ $errors-
>has('password') ? 'has-error' : '' }}">
                    <label class="required"
for="password">New {{ trans('cruds.user.fields.password') }}</label>

```


15.2.3 Controller code and element examples

15.2.3.1 Answers controller

```
<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyAnswerRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreAnswerRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateAnswerRequest;
use App\Models\Answer;
use App\Models\Project;
use App\Models\Question;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class AnswersController extends Controller
{
    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('answer_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $answers = Answer::with(['question', 'projects'])->get();

        return view('admin.answers.index', compact('answers'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('answer_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $questions = Question::pluck('title', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $projects = Project::pluck('shortname', 'id');

        return view('admin.answers.create', compact('questions',
'projects'));
    }

    public function store(StoreAnswerRequest $request)
    {
        $answer = Answer::create($request->all());
        $answer->projects()->sync($request->input('projects', []));

        return redirect()->route('admin.answers.index');
    }

    public function edit(Answer $answer)
    {
```

```

        abort_if(Gate::denies('answer_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $questions = Question::pluck('title', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $projects = Project::pluck('shortname', 'id');

        $answer->load('question', 'projects');

        return view('admin.answers.edit', compact('questions',
'projects', 'answer'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateAnswerRequest $request, Answer
$answer)
    {
        $answer->update($request->all());
        $answer->projects()->sync($request->input('projects', []));

        return redirect()->route('admin.answers.index');
    }

    public function show(Answer $answer)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('answer_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $answer->load('question', 'projects', 'answerBlocklists');

        return view('admin.answers.show', compact('answer'));
    }

    public function destroy(Answer $answer)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('answer_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $answer->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyAnswerRequest $request)
    {
        Answer::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.2 Blocklist controller

<?php

```

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyBlocklistRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreBlocklistRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateBlocklistRequest;
use App\Models\Answer;
use App\Models\Blocklist;
use App\Models\Question;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class BlocklistController extends Controller
{
    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('blocklist_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $blocklists = Blocklist::with(['questions', 'answers'])-
>get();

        return view('admin.blocklists.index',
compact('blocklists'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('blocklist_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $questions = Question::pluck('title', 'id');

        $answers = Answer::pluck('text', 'id');

        return view('admin.blocklists.create', compact('questions',
'answers'));
    }

    public function store(StoreBlocklistRequest $request)
    {
        $blocklist = Blocklist::create($request->all());
        $blocklist->questions()->sync($request->input('questions',
[]));
        $blocklist->answers()->sync($request->input('answers', []));

        return redirect()->route('admin.blocklists.index');
    }

    public function edit(Blocklist $blocklist)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('blocklist_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

```

```

        $questions = Question::pluck('title', 'id');

        $answers = Answer::pluck('text', 'id');

        $blocklist->load('questions', 'answers');

        return view('admin.blocklists.edit', compact('questions',
'answers', 'blocklist'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateBlocklistRequest $request,
Blocklist $blocklist)
    {
        $blocklist->update($request->all());
        $blocklist->questions()->sync($request->input('questions',
[]));
        $blocklist->answers()->sync($request->input('answers', []));

        return redirect()->route('admin.blocklists.index');
    }

    public function show(Blocklist $blocklist)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('blocklist_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $blocklist->load('questions', 'answers');

        return view('admin.blocklists.show', compact('blocklist'));
    }

    public function destroy(Blocklist $blocklist)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('blocklist_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $blocklist->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyBlocklistRequest
$request)
    {
        Blocklist::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.3 Countries controller

<?php

```

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyCountryRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreCountryRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateCountryRequest;
use App\Models\Country;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class CountriesController extends Controller
{
    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('country_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $countries = Country::all();

        return view('admin.countries.index', compact('countries'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('country_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.countries.create');
    }

    public function store(StoreCountryRequest $request)
    {
        $country = Country::create($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.countries.index');
    }

    public function edit(Country $country)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('country_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.countries.edit', compact('country'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateCountryRequest $request, Country
$country)
    {
        $country->update($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.countries.index');
    }

    public function show(Country $country)
    {

```

```

        abort_if(Gate::denies('country_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $country->load('organisersProjects');

        return view('admin.countries.show', compact('country'));
    }

    public function destroy(Country $country)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('country_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $country->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyCountryRequest $request)
    {
        Country::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.4 Domains controller

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Controllers\Traits\MediaUploadingTrait;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyDomainRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreDomainRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateDomainRequest;
use App\Models\Domain;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class DomainsController extends Controller
{
    use MediaUploadingTrait;

    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('domain_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::with(['media'])->get();
    }
}

```

```

        return view('admin.domains.index', compact('domains'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('domain_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.domains.create');
    }

    public function store(StoreDomainRequest $request)
    {
        $domain = Domain::create($request->all());

        if ($request->input('background', false)) {
            $domain->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('background')))-
>toMediaCollection('background'));
        }

        if ($media = $request->input('ck-media', false)) {
            Media::whereIn('id', $media)->update(['model_id' =>
$domain->id]);
        }

        return redirect()->route('admin.domains.index');
    }

    public function edit(Domain $domain)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('domain_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.domains.edit', compact('domain'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateDomainRequest $request, Domain
$domain)
    {
        $domain->update($request->all());

        if ($request->input('background', false)) {
            if (!$domain->background || $request-
>input('background') !== $domain->background->file_name) {
                if ($domain->background) {
                    $domain->background->delete();
                }
                $domain->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('background')))-
>toMediaCollection('background'));
            }
            elseif ($domain->background) {
                $domain->background->delete();
            }
        }
    }

```

```

        return redirect()->route('admin.domains.index');
    }

    public function show(Domain $domain)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('domain_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domain->load('domainQuestions');

        return view('admin.domains.show', compact('domain'));
    }

    public function destroy(Domain $domain)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('domain_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domain->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyDomainRequest $request)
    {
        Domain::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }

    public function storeCKEditorImages(Request $request)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('domain_create') &&
Gate::denies('domain_edit'), Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403
Forbidden');

        $model          = new Domain();
        $model->id        = $request->input('crud_id', 0);
        $model->exists    = true;
        $media           = $model->addMediaFromRequest('upload')-
>toMediaCollection('ck-media');

        return response()->json(['id' => $media->id, 'url' =>
$media->getUrl()], Response::HTTP_CREATED);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.5 Home controller

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

class HomeController

```

```

{
    public function index()
    {
        return view('admin.home');
    }
}

```

15.2.3.6 Permissions controller

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyPermissionRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StorePermissionRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdatePermissionRequest;
use App\Models\Permission;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class PermissionsController extends Controller
{
    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('permission_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $permissions = Permission::all();

        return view('admin.permissions.index',
compact('permissions'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('permission_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.permissions.create');
    }

    public function store(StorePermissionRequest $request)
    {
        $permission = Permission::create($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.permissions.index');
    }

    public function edit(Permission $permission)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('permission_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

```

```

        return view('admin.permissions.edit',
compact('permission'));
    }

    public function update(UpdatePermissionRequest $request,
Permission $permission)
    {
        $permission->update($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.permissions.index');
    }

    public function show(Permission $permission)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('permission_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.permissions.show',
compact('permission'));
    }

    public function destroy(Permission $permission)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('permission_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $permission->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyPermissionRequest
$request)
    {
        Permission::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.7 Projects controller

```
<?php
```

```

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Controllers\Traits\MediaUploadingTrait;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyProjectRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreProjectRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateProjectRequest;
use App\Models\Country;
use App\Models\Project;

```

```

use App\Models\User;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class ProjectsController extends Controller
{
    use MediaUploadingTrait;

    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('project_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $projects = Project::with(['user', 'organisers',
'created_by', 'media'])->get();

        return view('admin.projects.index', compact('projects'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('project_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $users = User::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $organisers = Country::pluck('name', 'id');

        return view('admin.projects.create', compact('users',
'organisers'));
    }

    public function store(StoreProjectRequest $request)
    {
        $project = Project::create($request->all());
        $project->organisers()->sync($request->input('organisers',
[]));
        if ($request->input('logo', false)) {
            $project->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('logo')))->toMediaCollection('logo');
        }

        if ($request->input('banner', false)) {
            $project->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('banner')))->toMediaCollection('banner');
        }

        if ($media = $request->input('ck-media', false)) {
            Media::whereIn('id', $media)->update(['model_id' =>
$project->id]);
        }

        return redirect()->route('admin.projects.index');
    }
}

```

```

}

public function edit(Project $project)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('project_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $users = User::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

    $organisers = Country::pluck('name', 'id');

    $project->load('user', 'organisers', 'created_by');

    return view('admin.projects.edit', compact('users',
'organisers', 'project'));
}

public function update(UpdateProjectRequest $request, Project
$project)
{
    $project->update($request->all());
    $project->organisers()->sync($request->input('organisers',
[]));
    if ($request->input('logo', false)) {
        if (!$project->logo || $request->input('logo') !==
$project->logo->file_name) {
            if ($project->logo) {
                $project->logo->delete();
            }
            $project->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('logo')))->toMediaCollection('logo');
        }
    } elseif ($project->logo) {
        $project->logo->delete();
    }

    if ($request->input('banner', false)) {
        if (!$project->banner || $request->input('banner') !==
$project->banner->file_name) {
            if ($project->banner) {
                $project->banner->delete();
            }
            $project->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('banner')))->toMediaCollection('banner');
        }
    } elseif ($project->banner) {
        $project->banner->delete();
    }

    return redirect()->route('admin.projects.index');
}

public function show(Project $project)
{

```

```

        abort_if(Gate::denies('project_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $project->load('user', 'organisers', 'created_by',
'projectResults', 'projectsAnswers');

        return view('admin.projects.show', compact('project'));
    }

    public function destroy(Project $project)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('project_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $project->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyProjectRequest $request)
    {
        Project::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }

    public function storeCKEditorImages(Request $request)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('project_create') &&
Gate::denies('project_edit'), Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403
Forbidden');

        $model          = new Project();
        $model->id        = $request->input('crud_id', 0);
        $model->exists    = true;
        $media           = $model->addMediaFromRequest('upload')-
>toMediaCollection('ck-media');

        return response()->json(['id' => $media->id, 'url' =>
$media->getUrl()], Response::HTTP_CREATED);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.8 Questions controller

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Controllers\Traits\MediaUploadingTrait;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyQuestionRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreQuestionRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateQuestionRequest;

```

```

use App\Models\Domain;
use App\Models\Question;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class QuestionsController extends Controller
{
    use MediaUploadingTrait;

    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('question_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $questions = Question::with(['domain'])->get();

        return view('admin.questions.index', compact('questions'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('question_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        return view('admin.questions.create', compact('domains'));
    }

    public function store(StoreQuestionRequest $request)
    {
        $question = Question::create($request->all());

        $answers = $request->only('answers');
        $updatedanswers = [];

        foreach ($answers['answers'] as $key => $answer) {
            if (null == $answer['text']) {
                unset($answers['answers'][$key]);
            } else {
                $updatedanswers[$key]['order'] = $answer['order'];
                $updatedanswers[$key]['question_id'] = $question-
>id;

                $updatedanswers[$key]['text'] = $answer['text'];
                $updatedanswers[$key]['weight'] = $answer['weight'];
                $answers[$key]['question_id'] = $question->id;
            }
        }

        if ($media = $request->input('ck-media', false)) {
            Media::whereIn('id', $media)->update(['model_id' =>
$question->id]);
        }
    }
}

```

```

        $question->questionAnswers()->createMany($updatedanswers);

        return redirect()->route('admin.questions.index');
    }

    public function edit(Question $question)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('question_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $question->load('domain');

        return view('admin.questions.edit', compact('domains',
'question'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateQuestionRequest $request, Question
$question)
    {
        $question->update($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.questions.index');
    }

    public function show(Question $question)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('question_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $question->load('domain', 'questionAnswers',
'questionBlocklists');

        return view('admin.questions.show', compact('question'));
    }

    public function destroy(Question $question)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('question_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $question->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyQuestionRequest $request)
    {
        Question::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }

```

```

public function storeCKEditorImages(Request $request)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('question_create') &&
Gate::denies('question_edit'), Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403
Forbidden');

    $model          = new Question();
    $model->id       = $request->input('crud_id', 0);
    $model->exists   = true;
    $media           = $model->addMediaFromRequest('upload')->
toMediaCollection('ck-media');

    return response()->json(['id' => $media->id, 'url' =>
$media->getUrl()], Response::HTTP_CREATED);
}
}

```

15.2.3.9 Recommendations controller

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Controllers\Traits\MediaUploadingTrait;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyRecommendationRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreRecommendationRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateRecommendationRequest;
use App\Models\Domain;
use App\Models\Question;
use App\Models\Recommendation;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class RecommendationsController extends Controller
{
    use MediaUploadingTrait;

    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('recommendation_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $recommendations = Recommendation::with(['domain',
'questions'])->get();

        return view('admin.recommendations.index',
compact('recommendations'));
    }

    public function create()
    {

```

```

        abort_if(Gate::denies('recommendation_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $questions = Question::pluck('title', 'id');

        return view('admin.recommendations.create',
compact('domains', 'questions'));
    }

    public function store(StoreRecommendationRequest $request)
    {
        $recommendation = Recommendation::create($request->all());
        $recommendation->questions()->sync($request-
>input('questions', []));
        if ($media = $request->input('ck-media', false)) {
            Media::whereIn('id', $media)->update(['model_id' =>
$recommendation->id]);
        }

        return redirect()->route('admin.recommendations.index');
    }

    public function edit(Recommendation $recommendation)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('recommendation_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $questions = Question::pluck('title', 'id');

        $recommendation->load('domain', 'questions');

        return view('admin.recommendations.edit', compact('domains',
'questions', 'recommendation'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateRecommendationRequest $request,
Recommendation $recommendation)
    {
        $recommendation->update($request->all());
        $recommendation->questions()->sync($request-
>input('questions', []));

        return redirect()->route('admin.recommendations.index');
    }

    public function show(Recommendation $recommendation)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('recommendation_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

```

```

        $recommendation->load('domain', 'questions');

        return view('admin.recommendations.show',
compact('recommendation'));
    }

    public function destroy(Recommendation $recommendation)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('recommendation_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $recommendation->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyRecommendationRequest
$request)
    {
        Recommendation::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }

    public function storeCKEditorImages(Request $request)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('recommendation_create') &&
Gate::denies('recommendation_edit'), Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403
Forbidden');

        $model          = new Recommendation();
        $model->id       = $request->input('crud_id', 0);
        $model->exists = true;
        $media           = $model->addMediaFromRequest('upload')->
toMediaCollection('ck-media');

        return response()->json(['id' => $media->id, 'url' =>
$media->getUrl()], Response::HTTP_CREATED);
    }
}

```

15.2.3.10 Results controller

```
<?php
```

```

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyResultRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreResultRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateResultRequest;
use App\Models\Domain;
use App\Models\Project;
use App\Models\Result;

```

```

use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class ResultsController extends Controller
{
    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('result_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $results = Result::with(['domain', 'project'])->get();

        return view('admin.results.index', compact('results'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('result_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $projects = Project::pluck('shortname', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        return view('admin.results.create', compact('domains',
'projects'));
    }

    public function store(StoreResultRequest $request)
    {
        $result = Result::create($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.results.index');
    }

    public function edit(Result $result)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('result_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $domains = Domain::pluck('name', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $projects = Project::pluck('shortname', 'id')-
>prepend(trans('global.pleaseSelect'), '');

        $result->load('domain', 'project');

        return view('admin.results.edit', compact('domains',
'projects', 'result'));
    }
}

```

```

    public function update(UpdateResultRequest $request, Result
$result)
    {
        $result->update($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.results.index');
    }

    public function show(Result $result)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('result_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $result->load('domain', 'project');

        return view('admin.results.show', compact('result'));
    }

    public function destroy(Result $result)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('result_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $result->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyResultRequest $request)
    {
        Result::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

[15.2.3.11 Roles controller](#)

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyRoleRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreRoleRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateRoleRequest;
use App\Models\Permission;
use App\Models\Role;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class RolesController extends Controller
{

```

```

public function index()
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('role_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $roles = Role::with(['permissions'])->get();

    return view('admin.roles.index', compact('roles'));
}

public function create()
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('role_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $permissions = Permission::pluck('title', 'id');

    return view('admin.roles.create', compact('permissions'));
}

public function store(StoreRoleRequest $request)
{
    $role = Role::create($request->all());
    $role->permissions()->sync($request->input('permissions',
[]));

    return redirect()->route('admin.roles.index');
}

public function edit(Role $role)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('role_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $permissions = Permission::pluck('title', 'id');

    $role->load('permissions');

    return view('admin.roles.edit', compact('permissions',
'role'));
}

public function update(UpdateRoleRequest $request, Role $role)
{
    $role->update($request->all());
    $role->permissions()->sync($request->input('permissions',
[]));

    return redirect()->route('admin.roles.index');
}

public function show(Role $role)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('role_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

```

```

        $role->load('permissions');

        return view('admin.roles.show', compact('role'));
    }

    public function destroy(Role $role)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('role_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $role->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyRoleRequest $request)
    {
        Role::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

[15.2.3.12 Topics controller](#)

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyTopicRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreTopicRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateTopicRequest;
use App\Models\Topic;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class TopicsController extends Controller
{
    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('topic_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $topics = Topic::all();

        return view('admin.topics.index', compact('topics'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('topic_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

```

```

        return view('admin.topics.create');
    }

    public function store(StoreTopicRequest $request)
    {
        $topic = Topic::create($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.topics.index');
    }

    public function edit(Topic $topic)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('topic_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.topics.edit', compact('topic'));
    }

    public function update(UpdateTopicRequest $request, Topic
$topic)
    {
        $topic->update($request->all());

        return redirect()->route('admin.topics.index');
    }

    public function show(Topic $topic)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('topic_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        return view('admin.topics.show', compact('topic'));
    }

    public function destroy(Topic $topic)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('topic_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $topic->delete();

        return back();
    }

    public function massDestroy(MassDestroyTopicRequest $request)
    {
        Topic::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }
}

```

[15.2.3.13 Users controller](#)

```

<?php

namespace App\Http\Controllers\Admin;

use App\Http\Controllers\Controller;
use App\Http\Controllers\Traits\MediaUploadingTrait;
use App\Http\Requests\MassDestroyUserRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\StoreUserRequest;
use App\Http\Requests\UpdateUserRequest;
use App\Models\Role;
use App\Models\User;
use Gate;
use Illuminate\Http\Request;
use Spatie\MediaLibrary\MediaCollections\Models\Media;
use Symfony\Component\HttpFoundation\Response;

class UsersController extends Controller
{
    use MediaUploadingTrait;

    public function index()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('user_access'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $users = User::with(['roles', 'media'])->get();

        return view('admin.users.index', compact('users'));
    }

    public function create()
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('user_create'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

        $roles = Role::pluck('title', 'id');

        return view('admin.users.create', compact('roles'));
    }

    public function store(StoreUserRequest $request)
    {
        $user = User::create($request->all());
        $user->roles()->sync($request->input('roles', []));
        if ($request->input('pic', false)) {
            $user->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('pic')))->toMediaCollection('pic'));
        }

        if ($media = $request->input('ck-media', false)) {
            Media::whereIn('id', $media)->update(['model_id' =>
$user->id]);
        }

        return redirect()->route('admin.users.index');
    }
}

```

```

public function edit(User $user)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('user_edit'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $roles = Role::pluck('title', 'id');

    $user->load('roles');

    return view('admin.users.edit', compact('roles', 'user'));
}

public function update(UpdateUserRequest $request, User $user)
{
    $user->update($request->all());
    $user->roles()->sync($request->input('roles', []));
    if ($request->input('pic', false)) {
        if (!$user->pic || $request->input('pic') !== $user-
>pic->file_name) {
            if ($user->pic) {
                $user->pic->delete();
            }
            $user->addMedia(storage_path('tmp/uploads/' .
basename($request->input('pic')))->toMediaCollection('pic');
        }
    } elseif ($user->pic) {
        $user->pic->delete();
    }

    return redirect()->route('admin.users.index');
}

public function show(User $user)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('user_show'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $user->load('roles', 'userProjects');

    return view('admin.users.show', compact('user'));
}

public function destroy(User $user)
{
    abort_if(Gate::denies('user_delete'),
Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403 Forbidden');

    $user->delete();

    return back();
}

public function massDestroy(MassDestroyUserRequest $request)
{
    User::whereIn('id', request('ids'))->delete();
}

```

```

        return response(null, Response::HTTP_NO_CONTENT);
    }

    public function storeCKEditorImages(Request $request)
    {
        abort_if(Gate::denies('user_create') &&
Gate::denies('user_edit'), Response::HTTP_FORBIDDEN, '403
Forbidden');

        $model          = new User();
        $model->id       = $request->input('crud_id', 0);
        $model->exists = true;
        $media           = $model->addMediaFromRequest('upload')-
>toMediaCollection('ck-media');

        return response()->json(['id' => $media->id, 'url' =>
$media->getUrl()], Response::HTTP_CREATED);
    }
}

```

15.3 Alquimics example code-base, inputs and outputs

15.3.1 Neural-network function code

```

function [J grad] = nnCostFunction(nn_params, ...
                                input_layer_size, ...
                                hidden_layer_size, ...
                                num_labels, ...
                                X, y, lambda)
% nnCostFunction implements the neural network cost function for a
three-layer
% neural network which performs classification
% [J grad] = nnCostFunction(nn_params, hidden_layer_size,
num_labels, ...
% X, y, lambda) computes the cost and gradient of the neural
network. The
% parameters for the neural network are "unrolled" into the vector
% nn_params and need to be converted back into the weight matrices.
%
% The returned parameter grad is an "unrolled" vector of the
% partial derivatives of the neural network.

% Reshape nn_params back into the parameters Theta1 and Theta2, the
weight matrices
% for our three-layer neural network
Theta1 = reshape(nn_params(1:hidden_layer_size * (input_layer_size +
1)), ...
                hidden_layer_size, (input_layer_size + 1));

Theta2 = reshape(nn_params((1 + (hidden_layer_size *
(input_layer_size + 1))):end), ...
                num_labels, (hidden_layer_size + 1));

% Setup some useful variables

```

```

m = size(X, 1);

J = 0;
Theta1_grad = zeros(size(Theta1));
Theta2_grad = zeros(size(Theta2));

% Part 1: Feedforward the neural network and return the cost in the
%         variable J.
%
% Part 2: Implement the backpropagation algorithm to compute the
%         gradients
%         Theta1_grad and Theta2_grad. We return the partial
%         derivatives of
%         the cost function with respect to Theta1 and Theta2 in
%         Theta1_grad and
%         Theta2_grad, respectively.
%
%         Note: The vector y passed into the function is a vector of
%         labels
%         containing values from 1..K. We map this vector into a
%         binary vector of 1's and 0's to be used with the neural
%         network
%         cost function.
%
% Part 3: Implement regularization with the cost function and
%         gradients.
%
%         We implement this around the code for
%         backpropagation. That is, we compute the gradients for
%         the regularization separately and then add them to
%         Theta1_grad
%         and Theta2_grad from Part 2.

X = [ones(m, 1) X];

for i=1:m
    % activations for each layer
    a1 = X(i,:)' ;
    z2 = Theta1 * a1;
    a2 = [1; sigmoid(z2)];
    z3 = Theta2 * a2;
    a3 = sigmoid(z3);
    % final layer activation is output vector
    h = a3;

    % create a boolean vector from a numeric label
    % yVec = (1:num_labels)' == y(i);
    % The following line is hardcoded to the case of exactly 5
    labels/domains
    yVec = [(y(i,1)); (y(i,2)); (y(i,3)); (y(i,4)); (y(i,5))];
    J = J + sum(-yVec .* log(h) - (1 - yVec) .* log(1 - h));

    % backpropagation
    delta3 = a3 - yVec;
    delta2 = Theta2' * delta3 .* (a2 .* (1 - a2));
    Theta2_grad = Theta2_grad + delta3 * a2';

```

```

    Theta1_grad = Theta1_grad + delta2(2:end) * a1';
end;

% scaling cost function and gradients
J = J / m;
Theta1_grad = Theta1_grad / m;
Theta2_grad = Theta2_grad / m;

% regularization
J = J + (lambda / (2 * m)) * (sumsq(Theta1(:, 2:end) (:)) +
sumsq(Theta2(:, 2:end) (:)));
Theta1_grad = Theta1_grad + (lambda / m) * [zeros(size(Theta1, 1),
1) Theta1(:, 2:end)];
Theta2_grad = Theta2_grad + (lambda / m) * [zeros(size(Theta2, 1),
1) Theta2(:, 2:end)];

%
=====

% Unroll gradients
grad = [Theta1_grad(:) ; Theta2_grad(:)];

end

```

15.3.2 Neural-network training code

```

%% MICS - Alquimics - neural-network learning and prediction

%% To execute the program run "mics" in a command window.

%% Initialisation
clear ; close all; clc

%% ===== Part 1: Loading and visualising data =====
% We start by first loading and visualising the dataset.
% We will be working with a dataset that contains
% citizen-science project characteristics.

% Load training data (3 training datasets) (needs to be changed if
the number
% of datasets is different)
fprintf('Loading data...\n')
pause (1);
X1=csvread('X01.csv');
X2=csvread('X02.csv');
X3=csvread('X03.csv');
X4=csvread('X04.csv');
X5=csvread('X05.csv');
X6=csvread('X06.csv');
X7=csvread('X07.csv');
X8=csvread('X08.csv');
X9=csvread('X09.csv');

% Unroll and merge input matrices

```

```

X = [X1'(:)' ; X2'(:)' ; X3'(:)' ; X4'(:)' ; X5'(:)' ; X6'(:)' ;
X7'(:)' ; X8'(:)' ; X9'(:)'];

y=csvread('Y.csv')./42;
m = size(X, 1);

%% Setup of the parameters
input_layer_size = size(X, 2); % number of questions x number of
options (20)
hidden_layer_size = 42; % 42 hidden units; this can be up
to 4000
num_labels = 5; % 5 labels for the domains, from 1
to 5
% If the number of domains changes, line 66 of file "nnCostFunction"
needs to
% be changed accordingly

% Randomly select 2 data points to display
% sel = randperm(size(X, 1));
% sel = sel(1:3);
% disp(X(sel, :));

% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 2: Loading parameters =====
% In this part, we randomly initialise the neural network
parameters.

fprintf('\nInitialising neural-network parameters...\n')
pause (1);
% Initialise the weights into variables Theta1 and Theta2
epsilon_init1 = 0.029;
Theta1 =
(2*epsilon_init1).*rand(hidden_layer_size,input_layer_size+1)-
epsilon_init1;
epsilon_init2 = 0.039;
Theta2 = (2*epsilon_init2).*rand(5,hidden_layer_size+1)-
epsilon_init2;

% Unroll parameters
initial_nn_params = [Theta1(:) ; Theta2(:)];

%% ===== Part 3: Compute cost (Feedforward)
=====
% We first start by implementing the
% feedforward part of the neural network that returns the cost
only.
% nnCostFunction.m returns the cost.

fprintf('\nStarting neural network...\n')
pause (1);
% Weight regularization parameter (we set this to 0 here).
% lambda = 0;

```

```

% J = nnCostFunction(initial_nn_params, input_layer_size,
hidden_layer_size, ...
%                 num_labels, X, y, lambda);

%fprintf(['Cost at initialisation parameters without regularisation:
%f '...
%         '\n\n'], J);

% fprintf('\nProgram paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 4: Implement regularisation =====
% We now check the regularisation with the cost.

fprintf('\nCalculating cost function with regularisation (to avoid
overfitting)... \n\n')
pause (1);
% Weight regularisation parameter (we set this to 1 here).
lambda = 1;

J = nnCostFunction(initial_nn_params, input_layer_size,
hidden_layer_size, ...
                 num_labels, X, y, lambda);

fprintf(['Cost function corresponding to initialisation parameters:
%f '...
%         '\n'], J);
pause (1);
% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 5: Sigmoid gradient =====
% We check the gradient for the sigmoid function.

fprintf('\nEvaluating sigmoid gradient... \n')
pause (1);
fprintf('\nSigmoid gradient at [-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]: ')
pause (1);
g = sigmoidGradient([-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]);
fprintf('%f ', g);

% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause(1);

%% ===== Part 6: Training NN =====
% We have now all the code necessary to train a neural
% network. To train the neural network, we will now use "fmincg".
% This advanced optimizer is able to train our cost functions
% efficiently as
% long as we provide it with the gradient computations.

fprintf('\n\nTraining neural network... \n\n')

% The number of iterations can be changed to a larger
% value to see how more training helps.

```

```

options = optimset('MaxIter', 10);

% Different values of lambda should be tried.
lambda = 0.07;

% Create "short hand" for the cost function to be minimized
costFunction = @(p) nnCostFunction(p, ...
    input_layer_size, ...
    hidden_layer_size, ...
    num_labels, X, y, lambda);

% Now, costFunction is a function that takes in only one argument
(the
% neural network parameters)
[nn_params, cost] = fmincg(costFunction, initial_nn_params,
options);

% Obtain Theta1 and Theta2 back from nn_params
Theta1 = reshape(nn_params(1:hidden_layer_size * (input_layer_size +
1)), ...
    hidden_layer_size, (input_layer_size + 1));

Theta2 = reshape(nn_params((1 + (hidden_layer_size *
(input_layer_size + 1))):end), ...
    num_labels, (hidden_layer_size + 1));

% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 7: Implement predict =====
% After training the neural network, we use it to predict
% the labels. The "predict" function uses the
% neural network to predict the labels of the training set. This
lets
% us compute the training set accuracy.

pred = predict(Theta1, Theta2, X);
pred42 = pred .*42;

fprintf('Training-set accuracy per domain: %f\n', (1 -
mean(sqrt(double(pred - y).^2))) * 100);

save Theta1.mat Theta1;
save Theta2.mat Theta2;

```

15.3.3 Score prediction code

```

%% MICS - Alquimics - neural-network learning and prediction

%% To execute the program run "mics" in a command window.

%% Initialisation
clear ; close all; clc

```

```

%% Setup of the parameters
input_layer_size = 3040;      % 152x20 questions x options
hidden_layer_size = 400;     % 400 hidden units
num_labels = 5;              % 5 labels for the domains, from 1 to
5
% If the number of domains changes, line 66 of file "nnCostFunction"
needs to
% be changed accordingly

%% ===== Part 1: Loading and visualising data =====
% We start by first loading and visualising the dataset.
% We will be working with a dataset that contains
% citizen-science project characteristics.

% Load training data
fprintf('Loading data...\n')
pause (1);
X1=csvread('X1.csv');
X2=csvread('X2.csv');
X3=csvread('X3.csv');

% Unroll and merge input matrices
X = [X1'(:)' ; X2'(:)' ; X3'(:)'];

y=csvread('Y.csv');
m = size(X, 1);

% Randomly select 2 data points to display
% sel = randperm(size(X, 1));
% sel = sel(1:3);
% disp(X(sel, :));

% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 2: Loading parameters =====
% In this part, we randomly initialise the neural network
parameters.

fprintf('\nInitialising neural-network parameters...\n')
pause (1);
% Initialise the weights into variables Theta1 and Theta2
epsilon_init1 = 0.029;
Theta1 = (2*epsilon_init1).*rand(400,3041)-epsilon_init1;
epsilon_init2 = 0.039;
Theta2 = (2*epsilon_init2).*rand(5,401)-epsilon_init2;

% Unroll parameters
initial_nn_params = [Theta1(:) ; Theta2(:)];

%% ===== Part 3: Compute cost (Feedforward) =====
% We first start by implementing the
% feedforward part of the neural network that returns the cost
only.

```

```

% nnCostFunction.m returns the cost.

fprintf('\nStarting neural network...\n')
pause (1);
% Weight regularization parameter (we set this to 0 here).
% lambda = 0;

% J = nnCostFunction(initial_nn_params, input_layer_size,
hidden_layer_size, ...
%                   num_labels, X, y, lambda);

%fprintf(['Cost at initialisation parameters without regularisation:
%f '...
%         '\n\n'], J);

% fprintf('\nProgram paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 4: Implement regularisation =====
% We now check the regularisation with the cost.

fprintf('\nCalculating cost function with regularisation (to avoid
overfitting)... \n\n')
pause (1);
% Weight regularisation parameter (we set this to 1 here).
lambda = 1;

J = nnCostFunction(initial_nn_params, input_layer_size,
hidden_layer_size, ...
                   num_labels, X, y, lambda);

fprintf(['Cost function corresponding to initialisation parameters:
%f '...
%         '\n'], J);
pause (1);
% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 5: Sigmoid gradient =====
% We check the gradient for the sigmoid function.

fprintf('\nEvaluating sigmoid gradient... \n')
pause (1);
fprintf('\nSigmoid gradient at [-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]: ')
pause (1);
g = sigmoidGradient([-1 -0.5 0 0.5 1]);
fprintf('%f ', g);

% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
pause(1);

%% ===== Part 6: Training NN =====
% We have now all the code necessary to train a neural
% network. To train the neural network, we will now use "fmincg".

```

```

% This advanced optimizer is able to train our cost functions
efficiently as
% long as we provide it with the gradient computations.

fprintf('\n\nTraining neural network... \n\n')

% The MaxIter can be changed to a larger
% value to see how more training helps.
options = optimset('MaxIter', 10);

% Different values of lambda should be tried.
lambda = 0.07;

% Create "short hand" for the cost function to be minimized
costFunction = @(p) nnCostFunction(p, ...
    input_layer_size, ...
    hidden_layer_size, ...
    num_labels, X, y, lambda);

% Now, costFunction is a function that takes in only one argument
(the
% neural network parameters)
[nn_params, cost] = fmincg(costFunction, initial_nn_params,
options);

% Obtain Theta1 and Theta2 back from nn_params
Theta1 = reshape(nn_params(1:hidden_layer_size * (input_layer_size +
1)), ...
    hidden_layer_size, (input_layer_size + 1));

Theta2 = reshape(nn_params((1 + (hidden_layer_size *
(input_layer_size + 1))):end), ...
    num_labels, (hidden_layer_size + 1));

% fprintf('Program paused. Press enter to continue.\n');
% pause;

%% ===== Part 7: Implement predict =====
% After training the neural network, we use it to predict
% the labels. The "predict" function uses the
% neural network to predict the labels of the training set. This
lets
% us compute the training set accuracy.

pred = predict(Theta1, Theta2, X);

fprintf('Training-set accuracy per domain: %f\n', (1 -
mean(sqrt(double(pred - y).^2))) * 100);

save Theta1.mat Theta1;
save Theta2.mat Theta2;

```

